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Abbreviations

APC	Article Processing Charge
B/C	Benefit/Cost ratio
CBA	Cost-Benefit Analysis
CSOs	Civil Society Organisations
CV	Contingent Valuation
EC	European Commission
EMBL-EBI	European Molecular Biology Laboratory – European Bioinformatics Institute
ENPV	Economic Net Present Value
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERR	Economic Rate of Return
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GDP	Gross domestic product
LRMC	Long-run marginal cost
OA	Open Access
OD	Open Data
OM	Open materials

OS	Open Science
OSD	Open Source Code
OSS	Open Source Software
PathOS	Open Science Impact Pathways (Horizon Europe Project)
RDI	Research, Development and Innovation
R&D	Research & Development
R&I	Research & Innovation
RCAAP	Repositórios Científicos de Acesso Aberto de Portugal
RDI	Research Development & Innovation
SDR	Social Discount Rate
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs)
WTA	Willingness to accept
WTP	Willingness to pay

Executive Summary

This is a methodological deliverable describing the **Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) framework** specifically designed, in the context of the [PathOS](#) project, to assess the impacts of Open Science initiatives (*hereafter the OS CBA framework*).

The OS CBA framework was initially designed by drawing on principles firmly rooted in CBA tradition, as well as on established approaches for evaluating investments in science and research.¹ Then, it has been tested on two real-world **Open Science practices**: UniProt (the *Universal Protein Resource*), a globally used, expert-curated protein database central to biomedical research, and RCAAP (*Repositório Científico de Acesso Aberto de Portugal*), a national, multidisciplinary repository consolidating Portuguese research outputs². Based on the lessons learned from these applications, the framework was subsequently **refined and further detailed**, and is presented in its consolidated form in this document.

The OS CBA framework fills a critical methodological gap in measuring the value of Open Science. It offers **a rigorous and consistent approach that accounts for both benefits and costs of OS projects across different types (Open Access, Open/FAIR Data, Open Code/Software, Citizen Science) and also enables comparison with a counterfactual scenario in which OS is not available**. It identifies typical cost and benefit categories and proposes appropriate methods for their measurement. On the cost side, it distinguishes between the investments made by OS providers (e.g., infrastructure setup and maintenance) and the time and effort required from users to learn how to use the resource effectively and engage with it (e.g. contribution to update and correction). On the benefit side, it highlights how users gain through cost savings, faster access to scientific data, improved reproducibility, streamlined data storage, and reduced access barriers.

The **primary focus of the OS CBA framework is on short-term measurable outcomes** of OS initiatives, such as efficiency gains with clear causal links. However, it is acknowledged that additional “enablement benefits” may also arise along the OS pathway. These include strategic advantages (e.g., development of new products and processes, development of patents, innovations, etc.) that emerge once initial OS efficiencies free up resources.

The document is structured as follows: **Section 1** introduces the rationale for a CBA framework and its role within the broader context of assessing OS impacts. **Section 2** outlines the CBA principles and the key features of its application to OS initiatives. **Section 3** describes the steps required to set up a CBA analysis and examines the specific challenges and considerations related to OS. **Section 4** focuses on the typical costs and benefits associated with OS practices and discusses potential methods that can be used for their quantification. **Section 5** concludes the document by providing a practical roadmap for the implementation of this framework into practice and outlining directions for future development. The document also includes two

¹ See Delugas et al., 2023 for an earlier version

² For more details, see Catalano et al 2025a, 2025b and 2025c.

Annexes: **Annex A** is a glossary that explains the technical terms used in Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) to help readers who are not familiar with this method; **Annex B** gives a technical overview, including formulas, of the methods used to measure the different costs and benefits.

1. Introduction

1.1. Why a CBA framework for OS?

Open Science (OS) is transforming the landscape of research and knowledge dissemination by accelerating scientific discovery, fostering innovation, and promoting transparency, inclusivity, and collaboration across disciplines. The strategic importance of OS has been increasingly acknowledged in global and regional policy frameworks. Notably, the UNESCO Open Science Outlook (2023) outlines a comprehensive vision for OS as a global public good, while the OECD (2015a) report emphasises the need for coordinated policy action to harness its full benefits. Since 2016, OS has become a cornerstone of the European Union's research and innovation agenda ([EC Open Vision](#)), with key initiatives such as Horizon Europe and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) aiming to embed open practices into the scientific process (European Commission, 2015; 2020).

Despite substantial progress over the past two decades (Paic, 2021), significant barriers continue to impede the widespread adoption and effectiveness of Open Science. These include infrastructural challenges (Bezuidenhout et al., 2017), incentive misalignments in academic evaluation systems (Moher et al., 2018; Pontika et al., 2015), and disciplinary disparities in openness practices (Tenopir et al., 2020; Chan et al., 2019). Moreover, concerns about a lack of skills and training, and the absence of clear legal and ethical frameworks further complicate efforts to mainstream Open Science (OECD, 2021; UNESCO, 2023).

While qualitative accounts of OS's societal and scientific contributions are growing, **empirical evidence on its economic impacts and the mechanisms through which these can be maximised remains limited and often lacks generalisability** (Fecher & Friesike, 2014; Vicente-Saez & Martinez-Fuentes, 2018).

Klebel et al. (2024) conducted a comprehensive review of both peer-reviewed and grey literature on the impacts of OS, revealing that existing evidence is predominantly focused on academic and societal,³ in particular on two types of OS: Open Access, which is mainly associated with academic impacts such as increased citation rates and research visibility, and Citizen Science, which is primarily linked to societal engagement and awareness. However, the review finds that **evidence of economic impacts⁴ is rare, mostly concentrated on the value**

³ See Klebel et al. (2025) for a detail review on academic impacts of OS and Cole et al. (2024) for further details on societal impacts of OS.

⁴ See for instance Tsipouri, L. et al 2025.

of open data and less so on open publications and open software; it is methodologically fragmented and often lacks comparability across studies.

On the subject of economic effects, Fell (2019) explores both perceived benefits and potential drawbacks, emphasising efficiency gains and the enabling role of OS in accelerating research processes and reducing duplication. His analysis identifies various mechanisms of impact through detailed case assessments, outlines enabling and inhibiting factors, and catalogues the methods and indicators employed in available studies. Nonetheless, the review concludes that **there is a lack of replicable, quantitative, and generalisable economic evaluations** of OS practices.

Building on this, Tsipouri et al. (2025) highlight that existing empirical evidence on the **economic benefits of OS is concentrated in specific sectors, particularly the life sciences**, where Open Access and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data practices have been more extensively adopted and assessed. Substantial gaps persist in other OS domains, such as Citizen Science and Open Evaluation, where economic impact assessments remain scarce or absent. Their analysis identifies three broad categories of economic impact: **efficiency gains, innovation enhancement, and contributions to broader economic growth** (see Box below).

Box 1: OS economic impacts

Efficiency gains emerge as one of the most consistently observed economic impacts across different OS practices. These gains are primarily achieved through **reductions in the time and costs** associated with accessing, sharing, and reusing research outputs. Among OS domains, the most robust and quantifiable evidence relates to Open and FAIR Data. Multiple studies have assessed the economic value generated by data services such as the British Atmospheric Data Centre, the Economic and Social Data Service, and the European Bioinformatics Institute (Beagrie and Houghton, 2013, 2016, 2021).⁵ These studies estimate time savings and user-reported values that often exceed operational costs by factors ranging from four to twelve. Similarly, in the context of Open Access, empirical analyses demonstrate time and cost savings for small and medium-sized enterprises and public sector institutions, including evidence from Denmark (Houghton et al., 2011) and the UK (Look and Marsh, 2012), and link OA availability to accelerated research output during the COVID-19 pandemic (Coccia, 2021). Open-Source Software (OSS) represents another domain where efficiency gains have been empirically demonstrated, particularly within firms, start-ups, and research-intensive organisations possessing strong absorptive capacities. Studies highlight cost savings in development and reduced time-to-market (Nagle, 2018; Conti et al., 2021; Chesbrough, 2023).

Enablement constitutes the second major category of economic impact associated with OS. This *pathway* reflects more transformative forms of change, where OS practices enable types of research that would otherwise be impossible. In the **short term**, this manifests in **stronger collaboration**

⁵ For instance, the quantitative economic approaches employed by Beagrie and Houghton (2021; 2016) included: estimates of access and use value, contingent valuation using stated preference techniques, an activity-costing approach to estimating the efficiency impacts of EMBL-EBI data and services, and a macro-economic approach that seeks to explore the impacts of EMBL-EBI use on returns to investment in research.

between academia and industry, greater interdisciplinarity, and the emergence of novel research questions and approaches driven by openness and accessibility. Over the **medium to long term**, these dynamics translate into **enhanced innovation**. Among the various OS practices, Open and FAIR Data have the strongest empirical backing. Studies consistently show that lowering barriers to high-quality datasets catalyzes downstream research and accelerates product development, particularly in high-value sectors such as genomics and pharmaceuticals (Williams, 2013; Arshad et al., 2016; Giovani, 2017). These data infrastructures enable a more rapid translation of research into innovation, fostering greater efficiency in R&D pipelines. They have similarly been linked to innovation outcomes. Empirical analyses show a correlation between OA publications and increased patent citations, suggesting enhanced uptake of scientific knowledge in commercial and technological development (Bryan & Özcan, 2021; Jahn et al., 2022). This indicates that removing paywalls may facilitate broader engagement with scientific findings beyond academia, including by industry actors and innovators. In addition, OSS plays a critical role in supporting innovation, particularly among start-ups and technology firms operating in emerging sectors. OSS reduces development costs, enhances interoperability, and fosters collaborative experimentation, all of which contribute to faster innovation cycles and lower barriers to entry (Conti et al., 2021).

The third, and more speculative, category of Open Science impact—**still within the enablement pathway**—is **economic growth**, which arises primarily through productivity gains enabled by greater accessibility, reuse, and efficiency in research. The theoretical rationale for this impact is compelling: by lowering transaction costs, reducing duplication, and accelerating knowledge diffusion, OS practices can foster more dynamic and responsive research ecosystems. However, empirical evidence remains limited, with much of the current analysis relying on macroeconomic modelling rather than direct observation. For instance, studies by Houghton and Sheehan (2006, 2009), and later work by Beagrie and Houghton (2021), suggest that even modest increases in openness—particularly through OA and FAIR Data—can lead to substantial long-term economic benefits at the national level, including gains in GDP and research productivity. Nevertheless, the validity of these findings is constrained by several methodological limitations. These include the reliance on assumed parameter values, the difficulty of isolating OS-specific effects within complex innovation systems, and the lack of longitudinal empirical data to support causal claims. As such, while the projected returns are promising, they should be interpreted with caution until more robust, empirical evidence becomes available.

Source: Authors

While the literature offers plausible evidence of the economic benefits of OS, establishing clear causal relationships remains a significant challenge. Much of the existing research relies on case studies, surveys and self-reported data, which are susceptible to bias and typically lack robust counterfactuals. Even more rigorous approaches struggle to isolate the specific contribution of OS due to the presence of confounding factors. As a result, the overall strength of causal evidence remains limited, underscoring the need for more robust, comparative, and counterfactual-based research designs. Notably, much of the current discussion is built on theoretical assumptions about the positive impacts of OS, without systematically comparing costs and benefits against alternative scenarios where similar outcomes might be achieved through conventional, non-OS approaches. This has likely contributed to high, yet insufficiently substantiated, expectations regarding OS's economic potential.

To address this evidence gap, we developed and tested, in the framework [PathOS](#) project, a **Cost-Benefit Analysis framework** that offers a structured and systematic approach to assessing the socio-economic impacts of OS initiatives by comparing their costs and benefits and contrasting them with a counterfactual scenario where OS is not available.

CBA is an analytical tool for assessing the economic and social desirability of an investment decision by comparing its costs with the related benefits in order to assess the net welfare change attributable to it (Giffoni and Vignetti 2019). It emerged from more than one hundred years of intellectual history (Dupuit, 1844 and 1853; Pigou, 1920; Little and Mirrlees, 1974) and has been widely adopted by international institutions and governments (EC 2014, EC 2021, EIB 2023, WHO 2006, Asian Development Bank 2013) as well as economists worldwide to evaluate the socio-economic impact of investment projects in traditional sectors (e.g. transport, environment, energy, health, education). More recently, CBA has been successfully adapted to evaluate investments in research, development, and innovation (RDI) and space infrastructure, with tailored frameworks that account for their unique characteristics (Florio et al. 2016, Florio 2019; Bastianin and Florio 2018; Florio and Sirtori, 2014; Florio, Forte and Sirtori, 2015; Battistoni et al., 2016).⁶ These methodological advances have also begun to inform assessments in the open research data domain. Recent examples include a comprehensive socio-economic evaluation of a national biobank (Li, 2024) and the valuation of open research data through contingent valuation methods (e.g. Palaiologk et al., 2012) and pricing models (Tu and Shen, 2024). The scoping review presented by Tsipouri et al (2025) shows several attempts to apply CBA, or some aspects of it, to some specific initiatives. It is, however, often combined with other approaches in a multi-method framework⁷.

Building on these developments and additional related works (e.g. JASPERS 2013; Griniece et al. 2020; OECD 2008, 2010, 2015b; ESA 2012, Morretta et al. 2023), we outline a set of practical guidelines for applying the CBA methodology to assess the impacts of OS initiatives, regardless of the specific practice or domain under evaluation.

Before detailing how this approach can be applied to OS, the following section outlines the contribution and relevance of CBA in the broader context of assessing OS impacts.

⁶ As a follow-up of such developments, the 2016 ESFRI roadmap recognised the contribution of CBA in providing robust evidence on the assessment of the socio-economic impacts of RIs. Moreover, the H2020 Work Programme 2018-2020 explicitly indicated the CBA as a basis for the Preparatory Phase of the ESFRI project.

⁷ See, for instance, EC (2018), which presents one of the first attempts to estimate the cost of not having FAIR research data for the EU economy, based on a series of measurable indicators, or Koudouri et al. (2021), who conducted an appraisal of OpenAIRE.

1.2. The CBA's role in assessing OS impacts

A comprehensive assessment of OS requires reconstructing its intervention logic, such as starting with an understanding of the underlying needs that OS aims to address, followed by identifying the activities undertaken, the immediate outputs they produce, the outcomes they generate, and ultimately the long-term impacts they seek to achieve. According to the intervention logic for OS developed and tested within the PathOS project (see Dekker et al., 2023; Karasz et al., 2024), OS impacts occur across different layers, reflecting the varying levels of responsibility, influence, and engagement of stakeholders involved. In this context, we can distinguish between short-term (direct) outcomes, long-term (indirect) outcomes, and broader impacts, as illustrated in Figure 1. **Short-term outcomes correspond to benefits related to the OS project itself from the perspective of responsible organisations and their direct users**, e.g., less time spent creating data due to the availability of FAIR data. They are in the sphere of control of the participating organisations, who implement and steer various activities. These effects can occur upstream—within the research process itself, influencing scientists engaged in data creation, training, or methodological development (e.g. through improved methods, training, or workflow tools)—or downstream, affecting direct users who adopt and apply openly shared outputs. **Long-term outcomes can be influenced by the OS project** (e.g., OS project responsible organisations can interact with the users and stakeholder groups in question and can seek to influence their behaviour), **although a direct causal link cannot always be established**, and these may also be shaped by other factors. For example, the registration of a new patent by a company may be enabled by open access to cutting-edge research outputs, but it is the result of additional research activities carried out by the company itself. **Impacts, covering lasting effects and structural changes manifesting in the economy and society, are enabled by Open Science research but require many additional activities, investments and factors to actually materialise**—for instance, the decrease in deaths caused by strokes induced by the introduction of new e-health technology.

As discussed in Dekker et al. (2023), PathOS adopts RI-PATHS's approach⁸ of tracing impact pathways, the causal links from resources and activities to outputs, outcomes, and long-term impacts, while identifying the mechanisms and conditions that enable these impacts. Drawing on the RI-PATHS model, PathOS identifies **three main impact pathways** within OS practices: academic, societal, and economic (see Karasz et al., 2024, for more details). These pathways represent the non-linear sequences connecting inputs to immediate, measurable outputs and their associated socio-economic outcomes. They also extend to broader, indirect impacts that are often difficult to quantify. Within the OS intervention logic developed by the PathOS project, the CBA framework is designed primarily to support the **appraisal of short-term outcomes** generated by projects that shape and operationalise OS practices, particularly those identified in the literature as **efficiency gains** (see Box 1 in Section 1.1). While long-term outcomes also

⁸ <https://ri-paths-tool.eu/en>

fall within the intervention's sphere of influence, they cannot be systematically assessed within the CBA framework unless their costs and effects can be clearly attributed. Therefore, the inclusion of long-term outcomes in the CBA is limited to cases where such attribution is feasible. Conversely, the assessment of broader impacts lies entirely outside the scope of the CBA and is addressed through alternative methodologies, which are integrated into the wider causal pathways' framework developed by PathOS⁹.

⁹ Cole et al (forthcoming 2025).

Figure 1: OS intervention logic

Source: Authors

2. Applying CBA to OS: Principles and Approach

2.1. The key principles

CBA allows for assessing whether benefits from an investment decision exceed costs, thereby showing whether it represents a net change for society as a whole. Being grounded in welfare economics, CBA considers the perspective of society at large rather than that of individual investors (Florio 2019). It boasts a rich history of *ex-ante* applications in informing the economic feasibility of investment decisions by quantitatively representing all societal costs and benefits. It has also been applied *ex-post*, following project implementation and closure, to evaluate the impacts of the investment undertaken. Indeed, CBA can be effectively conducted at any stage of a project's lifecycle, including during its implementation phase, or *in medias res*.

Although the application of this methodology has evolved over time and undergone different phases of experimentation, consolidation, and diffusion in a variety of institutional settings and sectors, **four core principles remain fundamental. These enduring principles continue to offer a robust and systematic framework, including in the context of assessing Open Science initiatives.** In particular, these features and principles include the following:

1. **Microeconomic perspective** on project assessment. Indirect effects (e.g. on secondary markets) and wider effects (e.g. induced impacts or effects on national and supranational gross domestic product) are often excluded. The reason is threefold. Firstly, most indirect and/or wider effects are usually transformed, redistributed, and capitalised forms of direct effects; thus, there is a need to limit double-counting issues. Secondly, there is little practice in translating wider effects into robust techniques for project appraisal. Thus, the choice is to avoid the analysis relying on assumptions whose reliability is difficult to check. Thirdly, CBA is based on the idea that GDP is a flawed measure of social welfare. For this reason, shadow prices, estimated according to a precise set of rules and methods, are adopted to value costs and benefits¹⁰.
2. **Socio-economic perspective.** CBA has the ultimate purpose of appraising the project's contribution to social welfare, which differs from financial measures such as GDP, value added or other aggregated financial outputs. This means that the 'financial' effects of a project are not the only ones considered. On the contrary, accounting prices in the CBA are not necessarily those observed on the market. This is either because many goods are 'non-market' goods¹¹ or because observable prices do not truly reflect the social

¹⁰ It should be noted however that, although impacts on GDP are not explicitly part of the assessment, the CBA implicitly considers them through the estimation of shadow prices (e.g. shadow wages – the shadow price of labour - are used to estimate the benefit from the creation of new jobs and employment).

¹¹ They are goods for which a market does not exist and therefore a price does not exist.

effect of the availability of an additional unit of a given good (i.e. market prices do not reveal the social opportunity cost of a given good). Most projects (in the traditional sector, like transport, environment, etc. and in OS) generate valuable outputs for which there are no observable prices. In that case, the CBA recurs to empirical estimations of opportunity costs, also referred to as *shadow prices*. Methods commonly adopted to estimate shadow prices involve measuring the people's willingness-to-pay for a given good (from the consumer perspective) or the marginal production costs (from the production perspective).

3. **Long-term perspective.** CBA adopts a long-run timeframe, often ranging from 10 to 30 years, to thoroughly evaluate a project. The exact duration can vary depending on the sector involved. Depending on the stage of the assessment—whether ex-ante (before implementation), mid-term, or ex-post (after completion)—CBA requires setting an appropriate time horizon, forecasting future costs and benefits, and applying suitable discount rates¹² to determine the present value of those future costs and benefits.
4. **Economic performance indicators expressed in monetary terms** (e.g. EUR). CBA assigns a monetary value (e.g. EUR) to all the positive (benefits) and negative (costs) effects of the intervention. These values are discounted and then totalled in order to calculate a net total effect, which is measured by means of three indicators, namely the Economic Net Present Value (ENPV), the Economic Rate of Return (ERR) and Benefit/Cost Ratio (B/C).
5. **Incremental approach.** CBA adopts a counterfactual¹³ perspective by comparing the scenario with the OS project to a scenario without it, i.e. what would have occurred in its absence. Therefore, the analysis focuses on the incremental costs and benefits resulting from the difference between the two scenarios. Performance indicators, such as net present values (NPVs), are therefore calculated based on these incremental differences, which reflect the project's true impact.

2.2. OS features in the CBA context

Open Science has been defined as the efforts taken by researchers, governments, research funding agencies or the scientific community itself to make the primary output of publicly funded research more widely accessible in digital format to the scientific community, the business sector or society more generally (OECD 2015). In other words, Open Science is an umbrella term for a variety of different practices in public and private research (Karasz et al., 2024) that refer to principles, approaches, and attitudes that prioritise transparency,

¹² The discount rate for valuing the contribution of the project to the social welfare is the Social Discount Rate, which reflects the social view on how future benefits and costs should be valued against present ones (EC, 2014 and 2021). For an estimation of this value to apply to projects in selected countries, see Catalano, J., & Pancotti, C. (2022).

¹³ It is worth pointing out that the counterfactual used in CBA is a hypothetical scenario; it is not a control group whose characteristics are observed and compared with those of the treated subjects.

collaboration, and openness in scientific research. The PathOS project identifies five different OS practices:

1. providing open access to research outputs (such as publications, data, software, models, algorithms, and workflows);
2. early and open sharing of research (for example, through preregistration, registered reports, pre-prints, and crowd-sourcing of solutions to a specific problem);
3. participation in open peer review;
4. measures to ensure the reproducibility of results;
5. involving citizens, civil society and end-users in the co-creation of R&I agendas and content, including citizen science.¹⁴

The adoption of a CBA framework for assessing the OS short-term outcomes requires a shift from the abstract notion of OS practices to the concrete implementation of OS projects. CBA is not intended to evaluate broad approaches or general attitudes but rather to analyse defined projects that operationalise these approaches. From this standpoint, the OS project—serving as the unit of analysis in the CBA—is typically a digital infrastructure initiative that has been explicitly funded or adopted to facilitate OS practices. Regardless of the terminology, they consistently refer to tangible undertakings aimed at implementing and enabling OS practices.

Examples of OS projects suitable for the application of CBA methodology (Box 2) include:

- Open repositories that preserve and provide unrestricted access to journal article reprints, preprints, and datasets;
- Open Data platforms offering free access to specific categories of research data;
- Free and open-source software tools designed to facilitate data processing and analysis.

In some instances, an OS project may also take the form of a national policy that mandates open-access publishing as a prerequisite for receiving public research funding.

Box 2: Moving from OS practices to OS projects

The examples below illustrate how high-level OS practices translate into identifiable projects that can be assessed within a CBA framework:

- **Open access to scientific literature.** Establishment of institutional or national repositories providing permanent and unrestricted access to peer-reviewed publications, preprints, and other research outputs.
- **Open research data.** Development of Open Data platforms offering free access to curated and interoperable datasets, often in key research domains such as climate, health, or social science.
- **Open-source research software.** Create and maintain community-developed software tools designed to support reproducible analysis and the dissemination of research methods (e.g. statistical packages, simulation tools).

¹⁴ In some cases, citizens science is not necessarily open.

- **Citizen science and participatory research.** Implementation of platforms for public engagement in research, including mobile applications or online portals enabling data collection and validation by non-specialists.
- **Policy incentives for openness.** Introduction of funding mechanisms that mandate open-access dissemination of publications and data as a precondition for receiving public research support.

Source: Authors

While in principle, the impacts of any change in the world can be evaluated using CBA, an OS project should possess some key characteristics to be considered suitable for this type of analysis. These features include:

- It delivers a **specific type of service** (e.g. access to raw data for an experiment/research, storage of data, processing and analysis of data, etc.).
- It targets **specific objectives** (e.g. innovation, solutions for societal challenges, etc.).
- It targets **specific types of users** as its effects clearly affect the well-being of specific categories of stakeholders (e.g. scientists, students, firms, citizens, and policymakers).
- Its **boundaries are recognisable**. In other words, all functional and technical components that are necessary to the achievement of its objectives and to the delivery of the intended service to the users can be identified.
- **Resources** employed to design/set up and maintain the OS practice **can be identified**.
- Immediate consequences produced by the project can be **observed, measured and directly attributed to it**.
- Observed effects materialise **over a specific time horizon**, which typically expands over a number of years.

Another important characteristic to consider in the evaluation of OS through the CBA methodology is the **degree of openness** of the project under analysis. This aspect directly influences the **breadth and diversity** of the potential pool of beneficiaries. Openness goes beyond simply providing access to scientific information—it also involves the extent to which such information can be **understood, validated, and effectively used**.

For example, an OS project may offer access to a complex research dataset. If the dataset is highly technical, only users with advanced expertise might be able to use it effectively, thus limiting its impact. However, if a simplified version is also made available to a broader audience, the **social impact** of the dataset could be significantly increased.

The degree of openness also pertains to the **conditions of access** to OS resources, which can shape both the **extent** and **distribution** of impacts across different beneficiary groups. For instance, in the case of open-source software, developers may have unrestricted access to the source code and can modify or extend it freely. Yet, this does not necessarily mean that all other users—such as those lacking coding skills—have free or easy access to the software itself. In some cases, access may require a **subscription or payment**, limiting its openness and, consequently, its impact.

Given its influence on **impact generation**, identifying the degree of openness is especially relevant when defining the **counterfactual scenario** (see Section 3.2) for estimating the net benefit of the OS project, as well as when categorising potential beneficiaries (see Section 3.3).

3. Setting the scene for CBA

3.1. Scope of analysis

When conducting any CBA, it is crucial to define the scope of the analysis, namely selecting the precise unit of analysis and the timing for which it is feasible and meaningful to carry out.

As outlined in Section 2.2, the OS projects may consist of a repository, a platform for data sharing, a software, a policy, a citizen science initiative, etc., which give shape to an OS practice (e.g. sharing of data, citizens' involvement, etc.). In selecting the specific unit of analysis, **all functional and technical components of the OS project** - that are necessary to the achievement of its objectives and to the delivery of the intended service to the users - should be considered. However, tracing the boundaries of an OS project can be more challenging than one might expect. In this sense, the following considerations apply:

- **The OS project may consist of several components which are functionally linked to each other**, thus meaning that they all contribute to the delivery of a unique type of service. Appraising such a project requires considering all the components. For instance, an open database might be a component of a broader range of OS services shared by the same institution, e.g., a digital infrastructure. Along with the Open Database, the institution may also share open tools or software¹⁵ to analyse the Open Data they supply. In this case, the different OS services are interconnected and contribute to the same service. For this reason, linking costs and benefits to a single output might be exceptionally challenging since the single OS output is part of the same intangible asset. Further, OS services often do not exist in isolation, and their mere existence (or simply their added-value, quality, richness of content) relies on the existence of other resources (Drysdale et al. 2020).
- **The project may consist of several components, each of them delivering a specific type of service** (e.g., access to raw data for an experiment/research, storage of data, processing and analysis of data, etc.) **and targeting specific objectives** (e.g., innovation, solutions for societal challenges, etc.) **or type of users** (e.g., students, scientists in academia and industry, etc.). In doing so, the components are not functionally related to other components, but each of them can be considered as a self-standing component. Appraising such a type of project requires considering each

¹⁵ They may be not completely open. For instance, the software can be free available, but its source is not open and cannot be modified.

component independently, but their aggregated impact can also be considered, if relevant.

Overall, selecting the **appropriate object of analysis means indicating which component(s) of a project the analysis refers to**. To provide a practical example, Elixir - the European life-sciences infrastructure for biological information – provides more than 400 open/FAIR bioinformatics resources. The CBA analysis may focus on one of these resources – such as a specific software, database, or platform – which is intended to provide a specific service¹⁶ or a combination of them if necessary. In the case that more than one resource – e.g., a combination of two/three databases or different software – contributes to the provision of a specific service, all these components may be considered in the analysis, since they are functionally related (e.g., without one of these components, the service cannot be delivered).

A more concrete example of the practical complexities involved in defining the functional boundaries of OS projects comes from the two case studies conducted within the framework of the PathOS project, which aimed to test the OS CBA framework. In particular, the case of **UniProt** illustrates the challenges of defining the unit of analysis for an OS resource in the biosciences, where data is continuously exchanged, integrated, and enriched by a wide range of contributors from various sources. RCAAP illustrates the example of an OS project composed of multiple components, each delivering distinct objectives.

Box 3: Defining the unit of analysis: the case of UniProt and RCAAP

UniProt is a freely accessible knowledge base that provides detailed information on the biological functions of proteins, with many entries derived from genome sequencing projects and scientific literature. Its databases—UniProtKB (including Swiss-Prot and TrEMBL), UniParc, UniRef, and Proteome—are built upon pre-existing datasets and are tightly interconnected with over 150 external databases, many of which also link back to UniProt.

The primary role of UniProt researchers is to assign unique identifiers, store data, and curate manual annotations to improve data quality. While defining UniProt's legal boundaries—those aligned with the UniProt Consortium—was relatively straightforward, defining its functional boundaries proved considerably more complex. This complexity stems from UniProt's deep integration with other platforms and the contributions of external researchers and institutions that generate and share the underlying data.

For the purposes of the CBA, it was considered inappropriate to include the value of research outputs developed by external sources and subsequently shared by UniProt, as most of this research would have been produced and disseminated independently of UniProt and is often available through other platforms.

Conversely, the time and effort invested by users in submitting updates, corrections, and enhancements that are functionally related to the database were deemed relevant for the analysis, as these contributions likely would not have occurred in the absence of UniProt. These community inputs significantly enhance the quality and utility of the database and are therefore included as part of UniProt's broader ecosystem.

¹⁶ For instance, one service from the lists available here <https://elixir-europe.org/services>

RCAAP is a network of Institutional Repositories (IR) that combines several Portuguese institutions under a common system. RCAAP provides several services, including free hosting of repositories for the voluntary institutions and a common Search Portal to browse the content of all the repositories at a single point of entry. Data hosting and journals hosting services are also provided, as well as several additional horizontal services, such as technical support and statistics. RCAAP is operated at the central level by the University of Minho and by the Foundation for National Scientific Computing (FCCN) – the digital unit of the National Research Funding agency of Portugal (FCT). The CBA analysis focused on the core of the RCAAP initiative—its network of institutional repositories and supporting services (e.g., RCAAP Portal, statistics, training, Helpdesk). The functional unit was defined as the storage and dissemination of scientific documents, aligning with RCAAP's primary objectives. Therefore, the analysis included the costs and benefits of operating, managing, and maintaining the system, including document deposit. Key benefits related to cost avoidance and increased visibility of Portuguese research. Data and journal hosting services were excluded for three reasons: (1) they are still in early development; (2) they serve different purposes—journal hosting supports peer review, while IRs focus on access and preservation; and (3) only IRs benefit from a legislative mandate (i.e., mandatory deposit), which affects user incentives.

Source: Authors based on Catalano et al (2025b) and Catalano et al (2025c)

3.2. Counterfactual scenario

As presented in Section 2.1, a key principle of CBA is the adoption of an incremental approach, whereby the costs and benefits of a project are assessed in comparison to a counterfactual scenario—i.e. the situation that would prevail in the absence of the project. This comparison aims to isolate the net change, capturing only the impacts that can be directly attributed to the intervention under analysis.

Defining the counterfactual scenario requires careful consideration of what would likely occur without the OS project. This involves addressing key “*what-if*” questions (e.g. Would the outcomes have materialised anyway, or in a similar form? Would the scale or intensity of the impact have been lower?) to guide this assessment, two main types of counterfactual scenarios are typically considered:

- **Zero-based scenario:** this scenario applies when an Open Science (OS) project provides access to research outputs that otherwise would not have existed or been accessible—essentially a “greenfield” context. In this case, the OS project is responsible for creating and sharing materials that either did not previously exist in the same form or were entirely inaccessible. Examples include repositories that collect shared code used across various programs. Without these repositories, accessing such code—often developed by unknown or dispersed researchers—would be nearly impossible unless it remained confined within specific organisations or research teams. Similarly, data repositories may aggregate datasets that were previously unavailable in consolidated form, even if the primary sources existed separately, such as datasets created through data scraping

or combining large volumes of information. Here, the incremental impact of the project corresponds directly to the OS project itself.

- **The closed (or do-nothing) scenario:** it applies when a scientific product is already available, but access to it requires payment. This typically includes scientific journals operating within subscription-based models, where users pay annual or monthly fees or pay per article to access content. Another example is licensed software, which requires payment for use. In this case, the counterfactual scenario incorporates the costs and benefits associated with the existing, paid-access system (*the status quo*). These are then compared with the costs and benefits of the Open Science project to determine the net effect.

Selecting the appropriate counterfactual scenario often requires **extensive consultation with experts involved in the OS project and with independent stakeholders**. Since counterfactuals are, by nature, hypothetical and not directly observable, such consultations are essential to formulate reasonable assumptions and identify the most plausible “next-best” alternative. Once the counterfactual scenario—either zero-based or closed—is established, it becomes the reference point against which all project-related costs and benefits are estimated.

The Box below illustrates the definition of the counterfactual scenario for two real OS resources, UniProt and RCAAP, each showcasing one of the two main types of counterfactual scenarios described above.

Box 4: Counterfactual scenarios in practice: the case of UniProt and RCAAP

In the **UniProt case study**, the chosen counterfactual scenario was a **zero-based (greenfield) scenario**. However, this decision required careful consideration due to UniProt’s nature as a knowledge base compiling information partially available elsewhere. At first glance, one might consider alternative paid or open-access resources providing similar protein data as suitable counterfactuals, since UniProt serves as a repository of existing information. Yet, extensive consultations with the UniProt Consortium, user surveys, interviews, and focus groups revealed that these alternatives typically offer fragmented data. Consolidating this dispersed information into a unified resource would require significant effort, be feasible only for large institutional actors, and would still fall short of UniProt’s quality. UniProt’s unique advantage lies not only in providing protein information but in integrating sequences with rich functional details, minimising duplication, and enhancing compatibility with other databases. It systematically structures information, offers detailed annotations for protein sequences, and compiles diverse research literature. For example, protein tag classifications help users quickly identify relevant terms, and linked PubMed references provide immediate access to key scholarly sources. Crucially, UniProt’s manual annotations represent original work developed collaboratively with external researchers, achieving an extraordinary level of depth and accuracy. Based on these findings, meaningful assessments of UniProt’s impact require comparison with equally integrated platforms; alternative counterfactual scenarios would capture only partial capabilities. The analysis concluded no single alternative matches UniProt’s integration and detail, leading to a composite counterfactual reflecting the user’s informational need. With this assumption, the CBA highlights UniProt’s net benefit over fragmented alternatives, without prescribing implications for specific UniProt data subsets accessible elsewhere.

In the case of RCAAP, Institutional Repositories were already beginning to emerge in Portugal before its establishment, making **the design of a counterfactual scenario challenging**. Constructing this counterfactual requires assumptions about how IRs would likely have developed and been used in Portugal without RCAAP, as well as potential alternatives for depositing and searching/downloading Portuguese scientific content. Since RCAAP aggregates various types of documents, it is likely that, without RCAAP, users would have dispersed their activities across multiple platforms rather than a single alternative. Respondents from different contexts—such as interviews, focus groups, and informal discussions—expressed varying opinions on the likely scope and pace of IR development in Portugal without RCAAP, particularly for smaller institutions facing significant resource constraints. Accordingly, the counterfactual scenario adopted assumes the objective would have been to maintain a comparable level of service—i.e., the digitisation of scientific resources via IRs—even without RCAAP. This assumption allows the CBA analysis to focus on the specific benefits RCAAP provides, especially the pooling of resources that enables a minimal level of service in digitising scientific materials. Moreover, the development of IRs without RCAAP is justifiable based on factors such as the rise of Open Science policies, mandates, and international trends. However, it should be noted that some institutions, particularly smaller ones, would likely have encountered significant challenges in achieving this goal without RCAAP's support. Thus, while IR development would have proceeded at a similar pace in the counterfactual scenario, it would have lacked the resource pooling and shared services provided by RCAAP. This has important cost and benefit implications regarding IR creation and operation. Without RCAAP, Portuguese institutions would have needed to allocate their own resources to run servers and to design, maintain, and upgrade their IRs, thereby losing the significant cost savings enabled by RCAAP's pooling of resources.

Source: Authors based on Catalano et al (2025b) and Catalano et al (2025c)

Both the UniProt and RCAAP case studies highlight a key challenge in defining the counterfactual scenario for large-scale OS projects: constructing a counterfactual by directly comparing fully closed and fully open alternatives is overly simplistic and does not capture the complexity involved. These projects consist of complex, multi-layered resources integrating numerous components and functions. As a result, the counterfactual typically involves multiple dispersed alternatives—some open, some closed, and others with varying levels of accessibility.

This reflects a broader characteristic of many OS initiatives: their value lies not only in making individual resources available but in aggregating, curating, and systematising them into a unified, interoperable structure. Thus, the real benefit often comes from moving from fragmentation to aggregation, rather than merely from closure to openness.

To conduct a targeted assessment of the transition from closed to open access, it is necessary to narrow the focus of the analysis to a specific component of the initiative—one that can be meaningfully compared to a closed alternative. Without such focus, the diversity and functional breadth of OS platforms can dilute the possibility of isolating a clear closed-open comparison.

3.3. OS targeted stakeholders

Assessing the impacts of an OS project requires identifying the stakeholders who may be positively or negatively affected. In this context, four main groups of agents—**potential beneficiaries or losers**—need to be identified, each playing a distinct role in shaping the demand for OS resources.¹⁷ This classification, originally proposed by OECD (2015), has been further tested and refined through the application of the OS CBA framework to selected OS projects.

- **Governments and Funders.** Being the primary source of funding for Open Science, they aim to maximise the (socio-economic) returns from science. This includes fostering stronger connections between science and innovation and promoting public engagement—ultimately enhancing trust in science and ensuring that research aligns with societal needs. Achieving this alignment requires the strategic allocation of resources and effective oversight to ensure investments deliver the intended societal benefits.
- **Industry (enterprises and professionals).** Industry stakeholders benefit from OS through access to new knowledge, which supports the development of innovative products and services. A closer connection between science and innovation is crucial, as companies rely on timely access to research findings to fuel their innovation pipelines. Reducing barriers to research access enhances knowledge spillovers. However, when companies are active participants in research, they may hesitate to fully engage in OS due to concerns about appropriability and competitive advantage.
- **Scientists.** Being the primary producers of knowledge, they advocate for a level playing field by removing barriers such as paywalls and addressing inequalities in gender, career progression, and geographic access. OS can make science more transparent and trustworthy, but it also introduces challenges. These include maintaining research quality and integrity, managing increased administrative burdens, and navigating field-specific constraints. Additionally, there are concerns that OS practices might reduce researchers' competitive advantage and that open outputs may not always receive the same peer recognition as those from traditional, closed models.
- **Citizens.** They may seek engagement with science at different stages of the research cycle—for instance, in idea conception, design, data collection, analysis, or dissemination—although not necessarily across all of these. They value transparency, access, and the opportunity to contribute to setting research priorities (e.g., through initiatives like the Dutch National Science Agenda). Public access to scientific knowledge

¹⁷ While OS projects frequently generate benefits that extend well beyond national borders, their financing is usually borne by one or a few countries. This asymmetry highlights the need for coordination mechanisms to ensure sustainable funding for initiatives whose impacts are global in nature.

is important for being informed on critical issues such as health, environment, and technology, and for fostering trust in scientific processes.

When mapping stakeholders, it is important to clarify the roles they play in relation to the OS initiative under assessment—whether through direct interaction with the resource or through their broader involvement in its ecosystem. Stakeholders may contribute by financing, developing, implementing, or maintaining the initiative. Identifying these roles is essential for collecting the data and information required for analysis (e.g., costs, user numbers, downloads, etc.).

In some cases, the project may result from international collaboration, with multiple institutions contributing to its funding and delivery. In distributed research infrastructures, responsibilities may be shared between a central hub and various nodes. In such scenarios, it is important to clearly outline the role of each institution or node involved.

Additional challenges emerge when users also act as contributors to the OS resource and may be affiliated with multiple institutions that do not necessarily provide financial support. For example, scientists worldwide may independently upload content to a shared repository. This widespread and informal collaboration can make tracking contributions and affiliations particularly difficult.

A further distinction arises from the roles users may take on. While many users access the resource for individual purposes, such as research, education, or innovation, some may also actively contribute to the resource's development. These users perform a dual function: they not only benefit from using the resource but also enhance its value by submitting, curating, or annotating content. In such cases, users may be granted deposit rights, enabling them to enrich the resource in a sustained and structured manner. This dual role highlights the participatory and co-productive character of many open research infrastructures, where value is generated collectively and continuously through ongoing user engagement.

Open research resources typically serve a broad and diverse user base, engaging with the resource in different ways and to varying extents. A useful first step is to distinguish layers of users based on their proximity to the core content and functionalities. Accurately identifying these user layers is crucial for estimating the benefits generated and appropriately attributing them across stakeholder groups.

While it is possible to define, in theoretical terms, the groups that may benefit (or lose) from OS projects, the transition from theory to practice—namely, establishing a concrete link between OS resources and their actual beneficiaries—requires careful methodological consideration (see Box below).

The inherently open and inclusive nature of OS resources, which aims to guarantee broad and non-discriminatory access, presents significant challenges when attempting to quantify demand and precisely identify beneficiaries. This complexity is particularly evident in the case

of beneficiaries who are not the funders or implementing bodies of the resource, which are easily identifiable, but rather end-users who exploit it for their own purposes.

To address this challenge, evaluators must consider how many agents benefit from the resource and the extent to which they benefit. This involves assessing factors such as user profiles, capabilities, ease of access, and level of engagement with the resource. Consequently, estimating both the number and characteristics of beneficiaries often requires the use of assumptions and inference models. This is because direct usage data are rarely available, as OS resources often allow access without registration or tracking mechanisms.

Box 5: Estimating the Users' population: evidence from UniProt and RCAAP

Estimating the composition and number of users of resources like UniProt or RCAAP is not straightforward. Being OS resources, both UniProt and RCAAP do not require user registration, so the user population is unknown, and usage must be tracked through web traffic metrics. While it ensures a maximum degree of openness and accessibility, it has several drawbacks. This way of measurement poses challenges in acknowledging characteristics such as geographical origin or professional background. Some of these characteristics can be captured by web metrics (especially country of origin), with some limitations, while others are far less tracked. In particular, understanding the composition of the users in terms of professional background is challenging and can typically only be performed using surveys, which can be subject to biases (e.g., self-selection).

Two main challenges complicated the task: the limitations of web-based metrics and the existence of multiple layers of users:

- **Limitations of web metrics.** Tracking users through web traffic led to an estimation of how many real users actually use the resources. Shared IP addresses within institutions might lead to undercounting, while dynamic IPs and multiple devices might inflate user numbers. Automated traffic, such as bots, further distorts figures, and access via untracked channels like FTP or APIs means some users can be missed entirely. Additionally, due to frequent data retention policies, anonymised IP addresses cannot be stored for many years, making it difficult to reconstruct long user series. Web metrics can also suffer from continuity issues. For instance, Google Analytics can induce breaks in the data by removing historical figures from previous years. In the case of UniProt, the estimation of the user base was carried out using a methodology adopted in Beagrie and Houghton (2021; 2016), which involves several adjustments: (i) neutralising the COVID-19 effect by halving the increase observed between 2019 and 2020; (ii) reducing web metrics by a factor of 80, following Fomitchev (2010); and (iii) adjusting for unregistered access by applying a correction factor of 2%, as done by Beagrie and Houghton (2021; 2016).
- **A layered user base.** In the case of UniProt, the user base is comprised of at least two layers, a common feature in bioinformatics. Primary users accessed UniProt directly and could be partially identified via logs and surveys. Secondary users benefited indirectly, for example, through other databases or tools integrating UniProt data, but were far more difficult to trace due to decentralised and global reuse. To address this, assumptions were made: indirect access to UniProt via other resources was assumed to be balanced by access to those resources via UniProt. Secondary users benefiting indirectly through primary users were excluded from estimates, as no reasonable assumptions could be formulated regarding their number. In the context of RCAAP, the layers of the user base reflected the structure of the system, which

involved a central portal with multiple participating institutional repositories. This implied specific challenges in collecting the data, which was split across multiple institutions, and sometimes not fully available or consistent (e.g., risk of double-counting for users accessing the resources from both the portal and the repositories). Centralised data was typically preferred in case of doubts due to its high quality and conservativeness.

In the case of RCAAP, the system also involved users with deposit rights, i.e., who could upload content such as papers or articles to the component institutional repositories. Estimating these users proved challenging for different reasons:

- Lack of centralised data: Data on the number of users with deposit rights was not fully available at the central level, especially for repositories which were not hosted centrally. This implied the need to extrapolate these users based on the available information, such as the number of documents or downloads for these repositories.
- Confusion between users with deposit rights and active users performing deposits: The available data only provided an overview of the number of users with deposit rights, but could not distinguish the number of users actually performing deposits. This can make attribution of costs and benefits to individual users challenging. This is further complicated by the fact that a single user may perform deposits on behalf of others.
- Lack of historical data: RCAAP only had data on the number of users with deposit rights at the present moment, giving a snapshot of the situation. The historical evolution was not available, implying the need to simulate this evolution based on available data.

Source: Authors based on Catalano et al (2025b) and Catalano et al (2025c)

3.4. Time horizon

Defining the time frame - over which the analysis will be meaningful - is a key step for setting the scene for the assessment. As mentioned in Section 1.2, the CBA analysis adopts a long-term perspective: it considers costs and benefits along their lifecycle, thus generated by the project over its useful technical and economic life. This time horizon encompasses the period in which the project is designed, launched and remains operational. The first year of the time horizon is when the project starts to be developed, such as when resources are disbursed for the design of such a project (e.g., design of protocols and procedures, conceptual study, feasibility studies, planning, etc.). The last year is when the project finishes materialising its impact or becomes obsolete and needs to be updated, expanded or redesigned. The time horizon of the analysis may vary. It can extend into the past, in which case the assessment is based on historical data (ex post CBA); into the future, where the analysis relies on projections and assumptions about likely developments (ex-ante CBA); or cover both past and future, combining evidence from historical data with forward-looking estimates (in media res CBA). Even if some of the benefits produced may last well beyond the operational phases in the field of science, a long but finite time horizon is considered reasonable for assessing impacts. **Such a time horizon is project-specific and changes greatly in accordance with the scientific domain.** When applying the framework in practice, the definition of the time horizon runs in parallel with data collection for

costs and benefits (see Section 4). Indeed, the choice of the time horizon for the analysis may also depend on the availability of historical cost data, as demonstrated by the cases of UniProt and RCAAP (see Box below).

Box 6: Setting the time horizon for the analysis: evidence from UniProt and RCAAP

The UniProt database—as we know it today—was established in 2002 by the UniProt Consortium to meet the growing need within the scientific community for a centralised repository of protein information. However, it builds on earlier databases that date back to 1984. A comprehensive CBA would ideally require data on costs and benefits beginning in 2002, when the current version of the resource was created. However, reconstructing setup costs for UniProt (2001–2002) and operational costs prior to 2017 proved challenging due to data limitations. As a result, the analysis focused on the period from 2017 to 2023, for which reliable data were available. Despite these limitations, the CBA approach was applied to assess whether UniProt’s benefits outweighed its operational costs during this timeframe.

RCAAP was launched in 2008 by the University of Minho and FCCN, building on earlier initiatives in Portugal and preparatory work carried out between 2006 and 2008. The platform was developed in several phases and is supported by academic institutions, legal developments, and ongoing service enhancements. Between 2009 and 2011, RCAAP introduced a number of new services to complement its core offerings, including quality control tools (e.g., OAI-PMH validator), hosting services (RCOMUM, SARDC, SARC), and horizontal services (SCEUR). From the mid-2010s onwards, RCAAP transitioned primarily into an exploitation and maintenance phase. Unlike UniProt, the available data for RCAAP enabled a fully-fledged CBA, including set-up costs and investment expenditures. This was made possible by accessing central budget data for RCAAP and reconstructing institutional repository budgets using literature, secondary data sources, and interviews with stakeholders. The time horizon for the CBA was set to be 20 years (2006-2026) in order to capture the full lifecycle of RCAAP. It followed standards typically applied to IT projects and was validated in consultation with RCAAP staff.

Source: Authors based on Catalano et al (2025b) and Catalano et al (2025c)

4. OS costs and benefits

The figure below provides an overview of the typical costs and benefits associated with an OS initiative in the short term.¹⁸ This classification is primarily drawn from a review of existing literature and has been validated through case studies of two selected OS resources, namely UniProt and RCAAP¹⁹. The extent to which this classification applies to a particular OS resource depends on the nature of the resource (e.g., repository, software, database), its scope, and the stakeholders involved (see Section 3).

Figure 2: Costs and Benefits of OS in a nutshell

Note: Benefits and associated costs refer to the short-term. **Source:** Authors

The following sections provide a detailed description of these costs and benefits, along with guidelines on suitable sources of information and methods that can be employed for data collection and quantification.

4.1. Typical Costs

In line with the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) recommendations for cost estimation (2019), two types of costs are typically associated with a project: **set-up costs and operational costs**. Setup costs include the initial expenditures related to planning, designing, and launching the resource—essentially all investments needed to establish the project. In contrast, operational costs cover the ongoing expenses required to maintain,

¹⁸ As discussed in Section 1.2, long-term outcomes (and the costs associated with their realization) cannot always be included in a CBA model due to uncertainty about their clear linkage to the project.

¹⁹ See Catalano et al 2022a, 2022b and 2022 c.

operate, and update the resource over time (see Sections 4.1.1 and 4.1.2 for more details). However, practical evidence from the assessment of OS also highlights the importance of distinguishing between two cost dimensions, such as **provider costs** and **user costs**:

The Table below provides a non-exhaustive list of such costs, as identified through empirical case studies. More details on their definition and methods for data collection are provided in the following section.

Table 2: Typical costs associated with OS projects

COSTS	DESCRIPTION	ESTIMATION METHOD
Provider costs		
Set-up costs	These include costs for office acquisition, legal fees associated with the consortium’s formation, other expenses for office and facilities, equipment and personnel during the start-up phase.	Accounting data; Budget analysis; Valuation of in-kind inputs; Market replacement cost; Interviews
Operational costs	They include salaries, equipment, consumables, publications, membership fees and contributions to partner organisations, travel (e.g. for project coordination, training, or dissemination activities), and overheads.	Accounting data; Budget analysis; Valuation of in-kind inputs; Market replacement cost; Interviews
User costs		
Training	Time spent to become an efficient user of the resource (e.g. to navigate it, download data, etc.)	User survey; Shadow wage valuation; Statistical inference from provider data; Benefit transfer ²⁰
Access	Time spent using and working with the resource	User survey; Shadow wage valuation; Statistical inference from provider data; Benefit transfer
Community contribution/Deposit costs	Time and effort required to curate and upload data/content to the resource	User survey; Shadow wage valuation; Statistical inference from provider data; Benefit transfer

Source: Authors **Note:** See Annex B for further details on estimation methods.

4.1.1. Provider costs

Provider costs refer to the actual financial expenditures borne by the institutions or entities responsible for developing and maintaining OS projects—such as data repositories, open-access journals, or collaborative platforms. These costs generally fall into two categories: **set-up costs** and **operational costs**. They typically cover infrastructure development, server and IT maintenance, personnel, and efforts to ensure compliance with data standards, legal

²⁰ Benefit transfer is a method used in CBA when primary valuation studies are not feasible due to time or resource constraints. It consists of applying estimates of economic values (e.g. willingness to pay, avoided costs, or non-market benefits) obtained in one context—the study site—to another context—the policy site. While it provides a practical way to approximate benefits, the validity of the transfer depends on the comparability of the two contexts in terms of population, environmental, and institutional characteristics.

obligations, and ethical frameworks. A more detailed breakdown of these cost categories is provided below.

SET-UP COSTS

Set-up costs refer to the range of expenditures incurred during the initial establishment of the OS project, as well as necessary reinvestments (to replace or upgrade) made throughout the project's lifecycle. These costs typically include acquiring durable tangible assets—such as servers, data storage infrastructure, and laboratory equipment—as well as intangible assets like software licenses, customised digital tools, and platform development. In addition, set-up costs may cover personnel recruitment and training, strategic planning, and initial compliance with legal, ethical, and data governance standards.

These costs are typically **derived from budget data** provided by the organisations managing the resources. When such data is partially available or missing, interviews with relevant stakeholders involved in the development and operation of the resource may be necessary to obtain reliable estimates.

These data are often used in the feasibility study when analysing the project from an ex-ante perspective or in the financial statement when examining the ex-post-performance. The relevant data to consider are the cash or in-kind expenditures encountered in individual accounting periods (years). These expenditures are necessary to acquire various types of assets, or if in-kind contributions are involved, their equivalent market value should be taken into account, even if they are not reported as financial flows.²¹

The unique nature of the OS projects poses some challenges to accurately estimating these costs.

- **Attribution of set-up costs:** A major challenge lies in accurately attributing set-up costs. OS initiatives often arise from decentralised and collaborative efforts, with initial investments distributed across multiple stakeholders and institutional levels rather than being borne by a single entity. This fragmented financial landscape complicates reporting and makes it difficult to determine the total upfront investment required to establish an OS resource.
- **Retrieving historical cost data:** OS initiatives often begin as small-scale efforts within research teams and gradually scale up to institutional or national levels. This organic growth can obscure early investments, especially when they are embedded within broader institutional operations. Financial records from these early phases are often incomplete, fragmented, or not detailed enough to be translated into meaningful economic cost estimates. Moreover, early reliance on in-kind contributions and

²¹ A residual value of the fixed investments must be included within the investment costs account for the end-year. The residual value reflects the capacity of the remaining service potential of fixed assets whose economic life is not yet completely exhausted.

volunteer work—typically not captured in formal accounting systems—further complicates efforts to build a comprehensive cost profile.

- **Temporal misalignment of costs:** Many OS-related expenditures do not align neatly with a single financial year. Costs may be distributed over several years or occur in different accounting periods than when the corresponding resources are deployed or become operational. This temporal mismatch requires the application of lifecycle costing and careful financial tracking to ensure an accurate understanding of long-term investment needs.
- **Relative magnitude of OS set-up costs:** evidence from applying the OS CBA framework to real-world practices suggests that the set-up costs for OS projects are generally modest—particularly when compared to traditional research infrastructures that demand significant capital investment in facilities and specialised equipment. OS initiatives are often launched through collaborative arrangements in which institutions provide in-kind resources such as staff time, technical infrastructure, and support services. These contributions help minimise upfront financial costs. However, while initial investments may be limited, OS projects often require significant upgrades over time—such as technical overhauls or system expansions—that resemble capital expenditures. Therefore, long-term sustainability planning should account for evolving and future cost requirements.

OPERATIONAL COSTS

Operational costs refer to all expenditures—both financial outflows and in-kind contributions—necessary to run and maintain the OS after its initial setup phase. From an ex-ante perspective, these costs can be estimated using historical unit costs, while ex-post evaluations may rely on financial statements and balance sheets, adjusted to follow the cash flow method to reflect actual spending and resource use over time.

These costs can be **fixed or variable**. Fixed costs remain stable regardless of service volume, provided capacity is unchanged, whereas variable costs fluctuate in proportion to output. Although average annual operating costs can be calculated, it is important to account for cost variability over the project lifecycle. In particular, early-stage operations often involve a ramp-up phase—typically spanning several years—during which costs may be higher until full operational capacity is reached.

The primary categories of these costs include **salaries, travel, equipment, consumables, publications, and overheads**. Estimating the value of in-kind contributions can be particularly difficult, as proven by the evidence of case studies: these contributions can fluctuate over time and may apply to any of the cost categories (e.g., senior personnel time, IT infrastructure and related operational costs, high-spec laptops, associated hardware, and computer supplies).

In addition to these common items, a range of social costs might be associated with academic and industry researchers. Indeed, deciding to publish via open access might involve a cost, such as the opportunity cost of patenting. Indeed, an Open Access publication could result in the loss

of potential earnings from a patent. Further, in the academic field where OS adoption is still in its infancy, publishing in an Open Access journal might be considered less valuable among peers and could even slow the career path of academic researchers. These costs are likely to be field-specific and related to the OS objective and nature.

4.1.2. Users' costs

User costs are not limited to direct monetary expenditures and can include efforts for which no financial transaction occurs. These encompass the value of time, effort, or other foregone opportunities (opportunity costs). In this context, they represent the time and effort required to engage with the OS ecosystem and may vary depending on the type of OS project. Such costs are borne by users of OS resources—such as researchers, academic institutions, or private stakeholders—during the operational phase of the project.

For example, in Open Access, Open/FAIR Data and Open Code/Software projects, user costs often include activities such as curating and uploading data, ensuring metadata quality and interoperability, or participating in collaborative governance structures. Users may also incur adaptation costs when transitioning to new OS tools or platforms, including the time needed to learn new systems or programming languages, modify existing workflows, and navigate legal or procedural uncertainties related to data reuse, attribution, and intellectual property rights. In Citizen Science projects, by contrast, user costs typically take the form of participation costs, depending on the type of engagement. For instance, in *Foldit*, participants invest time in solving scientific puzzles that contribute to protein structure prediction.²²

From a CBA perspective, user costs are usually measured as opportunity costs, regardless of whether or not they involve direct financial expenditure.²³ Accurately recognising and modelling these costs is essential to avoid overestimating the net benefits of OS resources and to ensure a more balanced and realistic evaluation.

By applying this framework to real OS practices, we identified four main categories of costs, outlined in the box below. The relevance of each cost type varies depending on the nature and design of the OS initiative. For instance, training and access costs were relevant across both types of OS projects examined in the case studies, whereas community and deposit costs were specific to particular features of individual projects (e.g., community contribution was significant for UniProt, while deposit costs were more relevant for RCAAP). This list is therefore illustrative rather than exhaustive.

²² See for details <https://fold.it/>

²³ The same cost can be also estimated in different ways. For instance, if the access fee of a commercial database is known, the cost of accessing an alternative Open Database becomes a negative cost, since its access fee is zero (provided that the market price of the alternative has been adjusted for distortions, or is considered undistorted). Alternatively, the same user cost can be assessed using the opportunity cost, by monetising the time spent accessing either the commercial or the Open Database. In this case, the net cost of access would be the difference in the value of time, which may be positive (still considered a user cost) or negative (constituting a benefit).

Box 7: User costs: evidence from case studies

Training Costs have been estimated with the time users spend learning how to navigate and utilise an OS resource. Training is typically provided either by the OS resource provider or by the users' home institutions. In most cases, the time burden is relatively low, as the more complex challenges often stem from broader issues—such as metadata standards, legal compliance, or institutional policies—rather than from the technical use of the system itself. In CBA, training costs are generally assumed to be similar in real-world and counterfactual scenarios and are often considered to cancel each other out in comparative assessments.

Accessing Costs represent the effort required to access an OS resource. Unlike potential alternatives - which may involve commercial fees or exist in fragmented forms - the monetary costs of OS practices are generally negligible or zero. Reliable estimates of these costs can be proxied through the opportunity cost of users' time, such as searching for, downloading, or otherwise retrieving content. These costs are relevant across a wide spectrum of users, including researchers, students, and the general public. From an analytical perspective, these costs are not computed in the analysis since already captured within the time savings accounted for on the benefit side. In this regard, it is worth pointing out that while these costs can be empirically estimated in real-world scenarios, deriving reasonable counterfactual estimates (i.e., what users would face without OS) requires additional assumptions (see Section 4.2.1).

Community contribution refers to the time and effort users invest in maintaining, improving, or enhancing the OS resource. From a CBA perspective, although these contributions are voluntary, they still require significant effort, expertise, and resources that could otherwise be used for different activities. Therefore, community contributions represent an opportunity cost. Unlike one-time onboarding activities, these contributions occur continuously throughout the resource's lifecycle and are thus classified as operating costs associated with the ongoing maintenance and updates of resources.

Deposit Costs refer to the time spent uploading content into the OS resource (e.g. repository), either by researchers or support staff. Since most repository systems rely on similar software and processes, deposit costs are usually consistent across alternative systems and therefore do not significantly influence the comparative outcomes of the CBA. User costs can be estimated through a dedicated survey in which users are asked to report the time spent learning to use the resource, integrating it into their workflows, and actively contributing to it (e.g., by submitting corrections, updates, or depositing materials).

Two primary approaches can be used to assign a monetary value to the time invested by users:

Salary-based valuation estimates the value of users' time based on their salary or wage rates. It requires information on users' professional profiles, including their sector of employment, role, and geographic location.

GDP per capita proxy: when detailed information on users' occupational profiles is unavailable, GDP per capita can be used as a proxy for the value of time. While less precise, this approach offers a standardised and practical alternative in the absence of granular data.

Source: Authors

4.1.3. Caveats in assessing OS costs

When identifying costs associated with OS initiatives, it is important to recognise that these often build upon pre-existing research, infrastructure, and community-driven efforts developed by a wide range of institutions. This interconnected structure necessitates careful consideration, as multiple stakeholders may be involved beyond the core developers and user communities. Evidence from the practical application of the CBA framework to OS highlights the need for specific methodological assumptions to guide cost analysis. The following assumptions may be considered:

- **Historical investments:** In many cases, Open Science projects are established as collections or aggregations of previous, uncoordinated, and fragmented initiatives. In such cases, these past investments are treated as sunk costs, such as past expenditures that would have occurred regardless of any specific Open Science initiative.
- **Ongoing research and development costs** from external institutions that produce tools, methodologies, or resources widely adopted within Open Science are also treated as sunk costs. While these contributions are vital to the ecosystem, they are often developed independently of any single Open Science effort and would likely continue regardless of a specific project's existence.
- **Maintenance and support costs** for third-party platforms or services that are used within the Open Science ecosystem are similarly considered sunk costs. Though these tools enhance collaboration and reproducibility, their costs are difficult to attribute precisely to any one initiative and often benefit multiple users and communities.

In line with the CBA principle (see section 2.1), the cost assessment should focus only on direct expenditures within the Open Science project itself and on tangible contributions from the scientific community that directly support its goals, such as Open Data sharing, code development, and community engagement.

The box below provides evidence from the grounds on the identification of the provider and users' costs, along with the challenges associated.

Box 8: Identifying costs in practice: evidence from UniProt and RCAAP

To accurately capture the costs associated with UniProt and RCAAP, a **careful, multi-perspective approach** was necessary to reflect the diverse range of stakeholders involved in establishing these resources. Both resources generate expenses for the providers as well as for the user communities.

In the case of UniProt, the managing consortium incurred the primary initial set-up costs, including the planning, design, and launch of the platform, as well as continued investments to support its development. The consortium also bears ongoing operational costs to ensure the platform remains functional and up to date. These include data curation, integration of annotations, enrichment of protein sequence information, and website maintenance. However, due to the integrated and distributed nature of the consortium, these expenditures have not been systematically recorded over time. This lack of detailed cost documentation makes it difficult to reconstruct a reliable time series of investment data, thereby limiting the feasibility of conducting a full CBA. In addition to provider costs, users of UniProt also incur costs—particularly in terms of time spent learning how to use the platform, accessing its resources, and contributing content through updates or corrections.

The structure of RCAAP is even more complex, with set-up costs distributed across multiple institutional levels. Central RCAAP activities included developing a hosting service for institutional repositories and a national portal for content aggregation. At the same time, individual Portuguese institutions were responsible for establishing and maintaining their own institutional repositories, often requiring local infrastructure, staff time, and technical support. Furthermore, the user community—particularly researchers and administrative staff—also bears costs, especially when uploading content and ensuring compliance with repository standards.

Both UniProt and RCAAP rely heavily on labour-intensive processes and build upon existing materials—such as databases and repositories—with the goal of enhancing accessibility and researchability. This approach optimises the use of available resources, avoiding the need to develop entirely new systems from scratch. While this approach helps reduce the costs associated with developing entirely new systems, it still requires substantial investment in personnel to organise, curate, and integrate existing information.

Both UniProt and RCAAP build on pre-existing content and operate through collaborative, interdependent networks. This interconnected nature required careful cost identification, as additional stakeholders beyond providers have been involved in their functioning and evolution over time. For the purposes of the CBA, the following methodological choices were taken:

1. **Non-recoverable past investments:** Costs related to datasets (for UniProt) and documents (for RCAAP) created before the platforms' existence were excluded, as these investments would have occurred regardless of the platforms.
2. **Scientific research costs:** The ongoing costs researchers and institutions incur to produce studies used by UniProt and RCAAP were also excluded, since this research would take place independently of the platforms.
3. **External database costs (UniProt only):** Costs of maintaining external databases cross-referenced by UniProt were treated as non-recoverable past investments, assuming reciprocal data sharing.

As a result, the CBA for UniProt included only costs recorded by the consortium and contributions from its user community. For RCAAP, the CBA included costs borne by the central system, individual institutional repositories, and users, such as content deposit.

Source: Authors based on Catalano et al (2025b) and Catalano et al (2025c)

4.2. Typical Benefits

Benefits refer to the advantages that society derives from a specific OS project. Once the potential beneficiaries are identified (see Section 3.3), a set of typical benefits can be associated with each group. Depending on the nature of the project, some benefits may be relevant to multiple types of target groups. As outlined in Section 1.1, the existing literature classifies the economic impacts of OS into three broad categories: efficiency gains, innovation enhancement, and broader contributions to economic growth.

As discussed in Section 2.1, the CBA adopts a microeconomic perspective, focusing only on those benefits that can be directly attributed to a project and for which a clear causal link can be identified. Within the intervention logic of OS, the primary role of CBA is to quantify short-term outcomes (see Section 1.2), particularly those identified in the literature as **efficiency gains**. These gains are mainly achieved through reductions in the time and costs associated with accessing, sharing, and reusing research outputs. In other words, OS enables both time and cost savings, contributing to lower expenses and more efficient resource use in scientific production.

For instance, the use of open software, tools, and data allows enterprises to save time in R&D and other operational areas. These savings also result from reduced working hours and the elimination of costs related to data storage and access. By optimising the use of OS services, organisations can streamline their workflows and improve productivity, making cost savings a key indicator of the social efficiency gains achieved through OS adoption.

The table below presents an overview of the various types of savings classified under efficiency gains, along with possible methodologies for their quantification. Because the boundaries between different benefit categories are often blurred, it is important to exercise caution when attributing benefits to different stakeholders to avoid double-counting. The following sections provide further detail, including warnings about double-counting and additional caveats related to the classification of these benefits.

Table 3: Typical efficiency gains associated with OS projects

BENEFIT	DESCRIPTION	ESTIMATION METHOD	BENEFICIARY TARGET GROUP(S)
Access cost savings	Reduction in financial and time-related barriers to accessing scientific outputs—including data, publications, software, and tools—achieved through open repositories, open-access publishing, and interoperable platforms that eliminate paywalls and restrictive licensing.	Avoided cost for accessing research outputs for free; Contingent Valuation; Cost of the internal research production; Benefit transfer.	Industry; Academics; Researchers; Professionals; Citizens.
Storage cost savings	Lower costs associated with digital storage and maintenance, enabled by shared Open Science infrastructures (e.g., institutional repositories, cloud services, and collaborative platforms) that reduce duplication of local storage and promote centralised or federated systems for long-term access and preservation.	Avoided cost for not storing research outputs; Cost of producing an in-house storage system; Benefit transfer.	Industry, Academics, Researchers, Professionals, Citizens.
Labour cost savings	Decrease in human resource requirements for accessing, managing, reusing, or curating scientific outputs, made possible by open workflows, standardised metadata, persistent identifiers, and high-quality documentation that streamline research processes and reduce repetitive or manual tasks.	Discrete Choice Experiment/Contingent Evaluation; Avoided cost for Personnel; Benefit transfer	Industry, Academics, Researchers, Professionals.
Transaction costs savings	Reduction in the time, coordination effort, and legal complexity involved in negotiating access, usage rights, or collaboration terms, thanks to the widespread adoption of Open Science principles and common standards that facilitate frictionless exchange and reuse.	Avoided cost for Personnel; Benefit transfer	Industry, Academics, Researchers, Professionals.

Note: See Annex B for further details on estimation methods. **Source:** Authors

4.2.1. Access cost-savings

The first type of efficiency gain associated with OS is **access cost savings**, which refers to the costs avoided when accessing essential knowledge or tools that, in a closed environment, would require payment or restricted access. This benefit primarily applies to three groups: (1) public research funders and governments, (2) enterprises, and (3) private citizens seeking access to research outputs.

By using OS services, researchers, enterprises, professionals, and citizens can avoid expenses typically associated with proprietary or paywalled resources. These include subscription fees, licensing charges, or pay-per-use fees that would be required in traditional closed-access systems. More broadly, this benefit captures the avoided cost of developing similar research

outputs independently, such as building a database internally because access to an existing one is not available or too costly.

One method for estimating the social value generated by OS—particularly with regard to access cost savings—is the **avoided cost method** (see Annex B for methodological details). This approach is based on the assumption that, in the absence of the OS initiative, beneficiaries would have to bear financial, temporal, or organisational costs to achieve the same goals or access comparable resources.

Box 9: Estimating access cost savings: evidence from UniProt

The access cost savings generated by UniProt were estimated by employing the avoided cost method, assessing the time saved by users compared to various counterfactual scenarios. As an integrated, open-access platform, UniProt reduces the need for users to consult multiple databases, thereby shortening search and access times and reducing the administrative burden associated with navigating diverse data environments. The calculation of access cost savings was grounded in the following steps and assumptions.

- **User access frequency as a determinant of time savings.** Time savings were found to be significantly influenced by how often users accessed UniProt. Survey data indicated that less frequent users tended to save more time per session, likely because they accessed large volumes of data only a few times per year (e.g. downloading the upgrade of an entire dataset), which would have required a substantial amount of time in a counterfactual scenario without the efficiency provided by UniProt. By contrast, users accessing UniProt several times per week are likely to save less time per session, as they typically download and integrate smaller volumes of data.
- **Distinction from labour cost savings.** For frequent users, it was difficult to distinguish between the time saved accessing the resource and the time saved in downstream research tasks. To prevent double-counting, the model applied access time savings only to users who accessed UniProt on a monthly basis or less.
- **Counterfactual scenarios.** The user survey explored three counterfactual scenarios: (1) accessing the same data through other open resources, (2) using paid resources, and (3) recreating the data independently. Reported time savings were highest when compared to data recreation and lowest when compared to alternative open-access options. The benefit was calculated using the average across all three scenarios.
- **Quantification of time savings.** Conditional on the assumption above, the time saved was calculated by calculating the most conservative figure between the median and the average number of hours used or saved per respondent, based on the weighted distribution of reported time intervals.
- **Monetisation of time.** Time savings were converted into monetary values by multiplying the average estimated hours saved by the corresponding hourly wage of users. Job titles were collected through the user survey, and wage data by job title, sector, and country of employment were retrieved from external sources (Eurostat, OECD, PayScale) to reflect country- and occupation-specific salary levels.
- **Aggregation of benefits.** Individual access cost savings were multiplied by the estimated number of users within each relevant segment to derive total savings. Where possible, results

were further disaggregated by user group (e.g., academia, public sector, private sector) to enhance the precision of benefit attribution.

Source: Authors based on Catalano et al (2025b)

When market prices are not available—either because no comparable service exists or the value of access is not adequately reflected in existing markets²⁴—alternative methods are needed to estimate the **social value of access cost savings**. One such method is the **Long-Run Marginal Cost (LRMC) approach**.

In economic terms, marginal cost refers to the additional cost required to produce one extra unit of a good or service. Applied to OS, the LRMC method estimates the **avoided production effort**—i.e., the costs that would have been incurred to produce an equivalent output if the OS resource were not available²⁵. For instance, when evaluating an open modelling platform for climate simulations, the LRMC method would consider the costs of independently developing the model in-house. These might include expenditures for expert personnel, external consultants, software development, model calibration and validation, and access to historical datasets needed to train the model. However, the LRMC method is not always the preferred approach for evaluating OS practices. Florio (2019), for example, cautions that focusing on the **producer side** may **underestimate the marginal social value** of the good, particularly in the case of open-source software. This limitation arises because production costs capture only the avoided monetary effort, while the wider social value may be much higher. In other words, LRMC provides a monetary estimate of avoided costs, but it may fail to reflect the broader benefits for users—such as the income, innovation potential, or utility generated through downstream applications—that extend beyond production costs alone.

An alternative approach, particularly relevant when market prices are absent or fail to reflect the true economic value of a benefit, is based on **willingness to pay (WTP)**. WTP represents the maximum monetary amount individuals are prepared to pay to obtain a specific benefit or avoid a particular cost (Boadway, 2006), and is thus a direct indicator of the perceived value of access. **Stated preference techniques** are commonly used to estimate WTP. These methodologies elicit preferences in **hypothetical scenarios** (see Annex B for methodological details). Among these, **contingent valuation (CV)** is widely regarded as a reference technique, especially for assessing the value of non-market goods or services viewed as indivisible wholes (Johnston, 2017). For example, the social value of an open database can be estimated by presenting users with a hypothetical situation in which access to the database becomes subject to a subscription fee. Users are then asked to indicate the maximum amount they would be

²⁴ The case of UniProt is a clear example of an OS project whose access value cannot be estimated using market prices. There is no commercial database offering an equivalent breadth and depth of information and data against which a comparison could be made.

²⁵ When considering open access papers there is a caveat associated to this method. Utilising the LRMC to produce papers that would otherwise be available only under a fee may introduce an issue related to the incentives raised by having open access papers. Indeed, one might be inclined to read more papers if they are freely available, as opposed to producing only what is strictly necessary.

willing to pay to retain access or the minimum amount they would be willing to accept to give up access permanently.²⁶ The responses collected through such surveys enable the calculation of aggregate WTP, offering an empirical foundation for estimating the total economic value generated by the OS resource as a public good.²⁷

4.2.2. Labour cost-savings

Another benefit associated with OS is **labour cost savings**. This benefit reflects the gain in opportunity costs that arise from exploiting open knowledge and tools. It may affect three different types of stakeholders: 1) public research funders and governments, 2) enterprises, and 3) professionals.

Labour cost savings represent value generated by reducing working hours and are a key indicator of productivity gains enabled by OS. These savings emerge when users are able to perform professional or research tasks more efficiently due to the functionalities provided by the OS service, such as streamlined access to structured data, reduced duplication of effort, improved interoperability across sources, or embedded tools that facilitate analysis and decision-making. For instance, access to shared code and protocols reduces the need to develop everything from scratch—users can instead build on existing work. Similarly, sharing data mining techniques automates information collection, reducing the need for manual data entry. The availability of open and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data also saves time for researchers and professionals by making relevant data easier to locate. OS further contributes to efficiency in designing research projects and writing publications, as the broader circulation of outputs—such as datasets, papers, and code—helps avoid duplication of effort.

From the user's perspective, these savings can be monetised by estimating the time saved and valuing it based on the *social cost of labour*, also known as *shadow wages*. This approach accounts for the opportunity cost of labour, which can differ from actual observed wages due to market distortions—such as minimum wage regulations, unemployment, or informal labour sectors. However, for skilled or highly skilled workers performing similar tasks, the shadow wage often approximates the market wage (EC 2014). When direct salary data is unavailable, or market wages are considered unreliable, alternative sources—such as salary data from private consultancies or national labour surveys—can be used²⁸. Though using national average wages is less precise, it remains a practical option in many cases. Under this framework, the social value of OS-related time savings can be expressed as the equivalent salary for the time saved. This benefit can be assessed using the **avoided cost method** (see Annex B for methodological details). For instance, if a researcher saves a full working day by using OS tools, the benefit

²⁶ See Annex B for further details on the differences between WTP and WTA.

²⁷ An example of this application is Beagrie and Houghton (2021).

²⁸ For instance, for the US (and some other geographical areas) labour market, PayScale might be a useful tool.

equals that researcher's daily wage. An alternative method for valuing time savings is to estimate users' **WTP** for such savings, as discussed in Section 4.2.1 for "access cost savings" (see Annex B for methodological details).

Box 10: Estimating labour cost savings: evidence from UniProt and RCAAP

Assessments of UniProt and RCAAP show that labour cost savings are the largest benefit of using Open Science resources, accounting for about 89% and 84% of total benefits, respectively. UniProt's strong integration in life sciences ensures reliable data, saving users time on verification and credibility checks. For RCAAP, savings come from centralising technical staff who manage multiple repositories more efficiently and from standardised services that simplify tasks like repository setup, streamlining overall management compared to institution-specific systems.

The estimation of labour cost savings for UniProt and RCAAP closely reflects the steps described in Box 9 for "access cost savings". We apply different assumptions for the annualisation of the weekly benefits:

- **Annualisation of time savings.** Weekly time savings were extrapolated over a standard working year, excluding holidays and leave. To avoid overestimation, the users were segmented into lower- and upper-bound scenarios reflecting different levels of resource use. Adjustments are informed by qualitative insights from interviews or surveys, capturing variation in usage patterns over time.

Source: Authors based on Catalano et al (2025b) and Catalano et al (2025c)

4.2.3. Transaction cost-savings

Cost savings can also come from **avoiding transaction costs**—such as time spent navigating copyright agreements or negotiating access to datasets, protocols, and other research outputs. Open Data, protocols, and software reduce these burdens by promoting shared, harmonised procedures for access. In contrast, closed systems often require more time-consuming, fragmented processes like negotiating terms or dealing with complex database restrictions.

The social value of avoided transaction costs should be assessed similarly to labour cost savings (see Section 4.2.2). While these savings are conceptually related to both labour and access cost savings, the distinctive nature and magnitude of transaction costs—particularly in large-scale collaborative research involving numerous institutions or facilities—justifies treating them as a separate benefit category.²⁹ Moreover, the estimation of transaction cost savings may require the adoption of specific assumptions, as these benefits may only apply to a segment of users or may only be relevant within particular operational contexts or time frames.

²⁹ See for instance the example in Lee (2015).

Box 11: Transaction cost savings: evidence from UniProt

Unlike many closed platforms, UniProt requires no user registration, institutional agreements, or case-by-case negotiations. Its compliance with FAIR principles ensures data is openly reusable, greatly reducing legal clarifications, access requests, and lengthy administrative processes.

To quantify this benefit conservatively, the following assumptions were made:

- **Identification of the user target.** The benefit was assigned only to the estimated share of new users each year, reflecting the one-time nature of institutional negotiations with other platforms.
- **Time benchmark.** One week of work per year was used as a benchmark for the time needed to negotiate access to a single alternative.
- **Quantification of time savings.** Conditional on the assumption above, the time saved was calculated by calculating the most conservative figure between the median and the average number of hours used or saved per respondent, based on the weighted distribution of reported time intervals.
- **Monetisation of time.** Time savings were monetised using average hourly salaries based on users' job roles, sectors, and countries.
- **Aggregation of benefits.** The benefit was applied to one alternative per new user; although shared benefits across multiple users in the same organisation were recognised, these were not separately monetised.

Source: Authors based on Catalano et al (2025b)

4.2.4. Storage cost-savings

Open Science practices, particularly Open Repositories, provide public access and retrieval of research outputs anytime, eliminating the need for private storage and reducing related expenses. This reduction—known as **storage cost savings**—arises from economies of scale and scope: repositories provide shared infrastructures that lower average costs and avoid duplication across institutions and users. These savings mainly apply to three groups: (1) public research funders and governments, (2) enterprises, and (3) private individuals accessing scientific knowledge.

The **avoided cost method** is appropriate for quantifying storage cost savings. This involves estimating the costs that would have been incurred without OS services—specifically, the cost of privately storing digital resources. To do this, the volume of storage needed is measured and multiplied by the market price of comparable commercial storage services. This requires targeted market research to find the closest alternatives, considering technical features as well as service factors like accessibility, security, and long-term preservation.

If no comparable commercial options exist, the LRMC method can be used. It entails calculating the cost of expanding a private storage system by one unit, including expenses for hardware, software, IT staff, data management, maintenance, and energy. This method offers a

conservative estimate by focusing on actual production costs users would face without open repositories.

Box 12: Storage cost savings: evidence from RCAAP

The RCAAP system pools storage costs by offering participating institutions shared hosting services for document repositories through SARI and RCOMUM. Storage cost savings were applied only to institutions using SARI or RCOMUM services. Institutions operating LOCAL repositories maintain their own servers, which are used as a benchmark to estimate savings.

A conservative approach was taken to estimate savings:

- It was assumed that without RCAAP, SARI and RCOMUM institutions would have created repositories under conditions similar to LOCAL institutions.
- The cost of a typical repository server (€5,000), based on the University of Minho's LOCAL repository (Alma Swan et al., 2016), was used.
- This inflation-adjusted server cost was applied to all SARI repositories according to their year of creation. Potential price drops in storage were not considered due to offsetting factors such as increased storage needs and evolving technology.
- For RCOMUM institutions, only 25% of the LOCAL server cost (€1,250) was applied, reflecting their smaller size. This factor was derived from comparing repository activity (downloads) between LOCAL and RCOMUM repositories.
- Every seven years after a repository's creation, a new server purchase (inflation-adjusted) was simulated to account for reinvestment cycles needed to maintain operations. This cycle length was based on interviews with repository managers (notably University of Porto) and supplier recommendations (e.g., Park Place Technologies).

Source: Authors based on Catalano et al (2025c)

4.2.5. Caveats in assessing efficiency gains

Although these benefits appear distinct in theory, a significant risk of overlap arises when they are empirically measured. This is because the benefits are inherently interrelated, and their boundaries often blur. Therefore, to avoid double-counting, the following considerations are essential when assessing them in practice:

- **Access cost savings:** When measured through contingent valuation, respondents may express broader values beyond direct access. For instance, the evaluation of EMBL-EBI's data resources by Beagrie and Houghton (2021) reported responses in which users associated the value of the resource with the **preservation of an entire scientific ecosystem**, indicating that their perceived benefits extended well beyond direct access. A further complication arises from the **risk of overlapping benefit categories**, particularly with **transaction cost savings**, which may be inadvertently included in respondents' stated willingness to pay. To minimise **double-counting**, it

is essential for the analyst to ensure **precise question framing** and to delineate clearly between overlapping benefit categories.

- **Stated preference techniques:** Obtaining reliable estimates can be challenging if the user population is unknown or poorly defined. In such cases, the risk of **selection bias** increases significantly, potentially undermining the validity of the benefit estimates. Under these circumstances, the applicability of stated preference methods may be limited, and alternative valuation approaches should be considered.
- **Storage vs. access cost savings:** A clear demarcation between storage and access cost savings is crucial to avoid inadvertently conflating the two, particularly when employing contingent valuation or LRMC methods. Clear definitions and specifications are necessary to ensure that these benefits are assessed separately and accurately.
- **Labour cost savings:** Double counting is reduced by carefully defining the time saved, excluding storage or quick access time and focusing only on active research time saved (e.g., time saved by using open, standardised methods).
- **Transaction costs savings:** attention must be paid to prevent overlap with access and labour cost savings. A clear definition of appraisal objectives is crucial, especially in survey-based valuations.
- **Users' profile:** especially in research fields with relatively scarce funding, users may tend to underestimate the social value of the service under evaluation.³⁰ Therefore, awareness of potential biases and careful survey design are essential to minimise their impact.

4.3. Enablement benefits

The CBA focuses on quantifying the direct impacts of Open Science, primarily efficiency gains. However, as described in Section 1.2, additional “enablement benefits” may also arise. These typically emerge later, after short-term efficiency gains free up resources for more strategic, higher-value activities. Enablement benefits reflect OS’s role in unlocking research and innovation potential, often resulting in increased productivity, enhanced collaboration, and the creation of new knowledge, products, and services.

The table below provides an overview of the enablement benefits which may be associated with OS, along with possible methodologies for their quantification.

³⁰ See, for instance, Beagrie and Houghton (2013) that assess the social value of the Archaeology Data Service.

Table 4: Typical enablement benefits

BENEFIT	DESCRIPTION	ESTIMATION METHOD	BENEFICIARY TARGET GROUP(S)
Development of new/improved products, services, technologies, start-ups and spin-offs	The value generated from the creation or enhancement of marketable outputs—such as products, services, technologies, or business ventures—that originate from or are accelerated by access to open research outputs, collaborative infrastructures, and knowledge exchange fostered by Open Science practices.	Survey of business; Statistical inference from company data; Benefit transfer	Industry (enterprises, including start-ups and spin-offs)
Patents	The value of novel inventions or processes that result from or are supported by the use of openly accessible scientific knowledge, data, or tools, highlighting the role of Open Science in enabling downstream innovation while maintaining intellectual property rights where appropriate.	Inventors' survey; Statistical inference from data on decision to renew patents or on economic terms of patent transactions; stock market valuation of market patent portfolio	Industry, Academics, Researchers, Professionals.

Source: Authors **Note:** See Annex B for further details on estimation methods

Enablement benefits are closely connected to knowledge spillovers, which arise from the widespread dissemination of research outputs. By promoting Open Access to scientific literature and data, OS lowers barriers to participation in research and enables a more inclusive, collaborative, and dynamic innovation ecosystem. For the scientific community, this results in broader opportunities for knowledge production, especially in early-stage research. For the private sector, it facilitates the uptake of public research, accelerates product development cycles, and enhances the likelihood of technological breakthroughs, including patent registrations. These effects are particularly visible in fields where OS resources—such as open datasets, open-source software, or shared protocols—serve as critical inputs to innovation processes.

From a conceptual perspective, the innovation process can be understood as a sequence of stages in which ideas and research outputs are transformed into valuable outcomes, such as new or significantly improved products, services, or processes (Janger et al., 2017; Oslo Manual, 2023). **OS resources contribute at various points along this chain**—either as enabling inputs or as catalysts for collaboration and iteration. Intermediate outputs (e.g. prototypes, patents, data models) often precede fully realised innovations, which must meet criteria such as market introduction or organisational implementation to be classified as such.

Nevertheless, attributing enablement benefits **solely to OS inputs** is inherently complex. These benefits are typically the outcome of multiple, interacting factors—including R&D investments, skilled personnel, infrastructure, and favourable institutional environments. As such, while OS may be a **necessary condition**, it is rarely sufficient on its own. Furthermore, the time lag between the use of OS resources and the materialisation of innovation outcomes complicates efforts to observe and measure impact, particularly in the short term.

These challenges call for caution in interpreting the causal link between OS and innovation. While existing literature provides indicative evidence (e.g. increased patent citations following Open Access publication, or enhanced start-up formation based on open datasets),³¹ establishing direct causality remains methodologically demanding. Robust empirical strategies (e.g. matched comparisons, longitudinal analysis, citation tracing) are needed to isolate the contribution of OS from other innovation drivers.

This document identifies and describes enablement benefits. However, fully attributing these benefits solely to Open Science remains methodologically challenging. Often, OS is just one of several factors driving innovation. Therefore, comparisons with OS project costs should only be made when OS can be clearly shown as the primary trigger of the observed benefits. Consequently, **incorporating enablement benefits into empirical CBA applications requires further methodological development tailored to the specific case.**

4.3.1. New products, services, technologies, start-ups, and spin-offs

OS projects play a critical role in generating knowledge spillovers that drive the development of new products, services, technologies, and even companies. This benefit is particularly relevant for two main groups: (1) enterprises and (2) public research funders and governments.

The rapid dissemination of knowledge enabled by OS—through Open Access to publications, data, software, and research outputs—accelerates innovation by making scientific resources widely and freely available. This openness lowers barriers such as subscription fees and restrictive licenses, fostering collaboration across academia and industry and enabling experimentation that might otherwise be cost-prohibitive. In doing so, OS expands the innovation frontier, especially by improving access to early-stage research.

OS practices also promote transparency and interoperability, facilitating more efficient collaboration among researchers, institutions, and businesses. These features contribute to reduced R&D costs and a more dynamic flow of ideas across sectors.

However, realising the full potential of OS often depends on **absorptive capacity**—the technical and organisational ability to identify, assimilate, and apply external knowledge. In its absence, particularly in complex or specialised fields, OS projects can act as catalysts for new ventures. Start-ups and spin-offs frequently emerge to bridge this gap, especially in response to high-value Open Data that requires expert interpretation.

³¹ Bryan and Ozcan (2021) show that after a free online availability of funded research by NIH, patents cite NIH-funded research 12% to 27% more often. Nonfunded research, funded research in journals unaffected by the mandate, and academic citations see no change. Similarly, Probst et al. (2023) examine the impact of the U.S. Department of Energy's open-access mandate finding that Scientific articles subject to the mandate were utilized on average 42% more in patents and articles subject to the mandate were not cited more frequently by other academic papers. Regarding new undertakings, the evidence is more qualitative: Garcia et al. (2018) highlight the rise of European SMEs that base their business models on open data from public bioinformatics databases provided by ELIXIR.

These enterprises serve as intermediaries, transforming complex data into actionable insights or customised services. For example, in the European life sciences sector, SMEs have formed around bioinformatics databases managed by EMBL-EBI and other ELIXIR Nodes (Garcia et al., 2018). Some specialise in data curation and client-specific customisation, while others integrate Open Data with proprietary sources or offer consultancy on data and software applications.

When the contribution of OS resources to innovation can be clearly established, the associated enablement benefit may be included in the CBA alongside related costs.

The economic value of this benefit is typically measured by estimating the incremental shadow profits generated by new or improved goods and services enabled by OS (see Annex B)³². *Incremental* refers to the difference in profits compared to a counterfactual scenario in which the OS input is unavailable or restricted. *Shadow* profits account for market distortions—such as regional disparities in innovation capacity or employment—that affect the true economic impact.

In cases involving new firm creation, the social value is estimated as the shadow profits generated by these enterprises over their expected lifetime, relative to a scenario without the OS resource.³³

4.3.2. Patents and licence deals

Another dimension of enablement benefits relates to patents and other forms of intellectual property. While particularly relevant for enterprises, this benefit can also extend to other actors. As noted by Bryan and Ozcan (2021), limited access to scientific publications poses a barrier to innovation—especially for underfunded institutions and small businesses (Frank, 2013). For smaller enterprises, access to scientific literature is crucial to engage with cutting-edge research, explore new technological paths, and recombine existing knowledge in novel ways. Open Science addresses this barrier by removing paywalls and licensing restrictions, enabling wider and more equitable participation in innovation.

By improving access to knowledge, OS enhances the conditions for developing patentable inventions. Patent filings not only generate private returns but also contribute to broader societal benefits through knowledge spillovers. However, **within a cost-benefit analysis framework, this type of benefit is difficult to isolate and quantify—particularly when trying to attribute innovation outcomes directly to a specific OS resource.**

A patent analysis may be conducted to trace the long-term outcomes of knowledge creation linked to a specific OS resource. This includes identifying and characterising the patents associated with it.³⁴ Only when a strong causal link can be established—connecting these

³² See Florio et al. (2016) for further details.

³³ Ibid.

³⁴ Patent analysis can track knowledge flows at different stages, including through forward citations, which are often used to assess long-term benefits. While this provides an indication of potential impact pathways, it is not readily incorporated into CBA due to the difficulty of establishing a direct causal link with the OS resource.

patents to the OS resource with reasonable confidence—can the benefit be estimated using the Marginal Social Value of Patents (see Annex B). This value captures both the private return to the enterprise and the wider societal benefit. Until such attribution is feasible, patent analysis serves as a valuable, though non-causal, indicator of potential impact.

Box 13: A patent analysis to track OS enablement benefits: evidence from UniProt.

As part of the UniProt case study, information was retrieved on patents that mentioned UniProt or its resources, using data from Lens and Orbis IP. Two approaches were applied. The first narrowed the search to UniProt-related keywords in titles and abstracts of patents filed after the establishment of UniProt, i.e., between 2002 and 2021, while the second extended it to the full text, including descriptions and claims, of patents filed since the creation of Swiss-Pat, i.e., between 1988 and 2022. The narrower approach identified fewer patents than the extended analysis (44,747 vs 78 distinct patent families), but it highlighted the higher value of UniProt resources by focusing on cases where UniProt plays a central role in innovation. The explicit mentioning of UniProt in titles and abstracts suggests a strong reliance on its resources, reinforcing its significance in patented discoveries. Together, these analyses provide a comprehensive view of UniProt's contribution to innovation. To avoid double-counting, the analysis considers the priority claim of each patent family, i.e., the first patent application ever filed among those belonging to the same patent family. Whereas a patent publication is the official disclosure of the patent application or granted patent, typically made public 18 months after the initial filing, the patent family organises related patent applications from different countries that protect the same invention based on a shared “priority” application, often the first filed. This family structure allows patent offices and researchers to track all versions of an invention globally under a unified group.

Source: Authors based on Catalano et al (2025b)

4.4. CBA results

Once all costs and benefits have been quantified and expressed in monetary terms, it becomes possible to determine whether the project generates a net benefit for society. This involves comparing the present value³⁵ of costs and benefits over the defined time horizon and calculating three performance indicators, including ENPV, ERR and B/C ratio (see Box below for details).

Box 14: CBA performance indicators

(1) Economic Net Present Value (ENPV): This represents the difference between the discounted total social benefits and costs. A positive ENPV indicates that the project is expected to increase social welfare, while a negative ENPV suggests that the resources could be better used elsewhere. Mathematically, ENPV is calculated as:

$$ENPV = \sum_{t=0}^T \frac{B_t - C_t}{(1 + r)^t}$$

³⁵ An appropriate discount rate can be retrieved by national or EU-level guidance (see European Commission 2021; 2014) from ad-hoc calculation by countries (see Catalano and Pancotti, 2022)

where B_t and C_t are benefits and costs at time t , r is the discount rate, and T is the project time-horizon.

(2) Economic Rate of Return (ERR): The internal rate of return that makes the Economic Net Present Value (ENPV) equal to zero. It corresponds to the discount rate r that satisfies the ENPV equation and indicates the project's break-even point in economic terms

$$0 = \sum_{t=0}^T \frac{B_t - C_t}{(1+r)^t}$$

(3) B/C ratio, i.e. the ratio between discounted economic benefits and costs, expressed as.

$$B/C = \frac{\sum_{t=0}^T \frac{B_t}{(1+r)^t}}{\sum_{t=0}^T \frac{C_t}{(1+r)^t}}$$

A B/C ratio greater than 1 implies the project is socially beneficial, while a ratio less than 1 indicates that costs exceed benefits. Although ENPV is the primary measure, the B/C ratio is particularly useful for comparing projects of different sizes.

Source: Authors

The calculation of economic performance indicators is typically complemented by sensitivity and risk analyses, which assess how robust the conclusions remain when key assumptions or uncertain variables vary within a defined range. Since cost-benefit analyses often depend on estimates and projections that can be affected by data limitations or unforeseen factors, these analyses help identify which assumptions have the greatest influence on the results. This process enhances confidence in the findings by showing whether the overall conclusions hold true across a variety of plausible scenarios or if they are highly sensitive to specific inputs³⁶.

Evidence from the application of this OS framework to real OS practices has shown that conducting a full cost-benefit analysis is often not feasible due to data limitations. In particular, set-up costs and in-kind contributions may not be systematically recorded (see Section 4.1.1), making it impossible to accurately estimate key indicators like NPV or the B/C ratio. In such situations, alternative metrics can be employed to provide policymakers and funders with insights into the socio-economic value of the OS project. One such alternative is the average annual net benefit per user—a simplified yet informative measure especially useful when only limited time-series data is available. This indicator (see formula below) allows stakeholders to evaluate the per-user value of the OS initiative without relying on long-term forecasts or discounting. Moreover, it can be broken down by user type or adjusted for differences in usage intensity to provide a more nuanced understanding.

$$\text{Average Annual Net Benefit per User} = \frac{\bar{B} - \bar{C}}{U}$$

³⁶ For more detailed guidance on conducting sensitivity and risk analyses, please refer to general CBA guidelines published by the European Commission (EC 2014 and 2021).

When using this alternative indicator, it is crucial to clearly specify which costs and benefits are included in the calculation. For instance, in the UniProt case study³⁷, the average annual net benefit per user was estimated over seven years, excluding the set-up phase, meaning the indicator only compared benefits with operational costs. In such cases, the quantitative results should be accompanied by a qualitative discussion that explains the assumptions made and how to interpret the findings.

Another approach is to calculate a partial benefit-cost (B/C) ratio, which is especially useful when some cost components, like set-up costs, are missing but benefit estimates are complete. Here, the B/C ratio compares total benefits against operational costs only. This method can be appropriate when set-up costs are relatively small compared to ongoing operational expenses, as is often the case in OS projects (see Section 4.1.1).

Partial B/C ratios can also help evaluate the relative significance of specific benefit categories in relation to available cost data.³⁸ For example, separate B/C ratios can be calculated for access cost savings, labour cost savings, or storage cost savings, using either partial or full cost data as the denominator. This disaggregated approach offers a more detailed understanding of the value generated by individual benefits and can provide valuable insights even when a comprehensive CBA is not feasible.

5. Conclusions

The OS CBA framework described in this document is expected to **fill an important gap in the literature on OS impacts**. It provides a systematic and comprehensive assessment of Open Science—accounting not only for benefits but also for associated costs, and critically, comparing them to a scenario where Open Science is not available. It is important to emphasise that **this framework is not intended to serve as a standalone tool** for appraising all possible effects of Open Science. Instead, it is designed to **integrate into the broader OS Pathway Assessment Framework** developed as part of the PathOS project. It serves as a crucial initial step to quantifying the direct and measurable impacts of OS resources. It complements other methodologies (e.g. patent citation analysis, case studies, etc.)—that are better suited to capturing indirect and long-term OS impacts.

To support the operationalisation and wider adoption of the OS CBA framework, we provide – in what follows - a **practical roadmap** to guide its implementation along with tips to keep in mind (Section 6.1). While the current framework marks significant progress toward more rigorous evaluation of Open Science initiatives, further actions are needed to improve its usability, scalability, and practical relevance. Section 6.2 outlines **targeted recommendations** to strengthen the framework's capacity to enhance transparency and support evidence-based resource allocation in the Open Science ecosystem.

³⁷ See Catalano et al (2025b), <https://zenodo.org/records/15732022>

³⁸ This approach has been adopted in Beagrie and Houghton (2021;2016).

5.1. OS CBA roadmap

Applying the CBA methodology to assess OS initiatives involves a structured, multi-step process which can be summarised in the following key steps (see Figure below).

Figure 3: The CBA roadmap to OS

Source: Authors

1. Identify the unit of analysis

The first step is to clearly define the unit of analysis, which sets the precise scope and focus of the assessment. This requires explicitly delineating the functional and legal boundaries of the OS resource or platform under evaluation. Given that OS initiatives typically operate within complex ecosystems involving numerous partners, contributors, and interconnected activities, it is essential to distinguish core activities directly linked to the resource from those that would have occurred independently (e.g., research outputs that would have been produced regardless of the OS platform). Engaging stakeholders—such as OS managers, users, and funders—through workshops or focus groups can help reach consensus on the core components to include.

2. Select a realistic benchmark

The second step involves defining the counterfactual scenario — such as what would happen in the absence of the OS initiative. This serves as the essential benchmark against which the net changes produced by the initiative can be measured. Constructing this hypothetical baseline requires careful consideration because:

- OS tools often have no direct equivalents so that alternatives may be fragmented, less efficient, or more costly.
- It is important to consider how different user groups would access similar services or data if the OS platform did not exist, accounting for variations in user needs and behaviours.

- Transparency about assumptions and limitations is crucial, as different stakeholders may have different opinions about the most plausible alternative scenarios.

3. Map users and stakeholders

The third step is to identify and map all stakeholders who may be affected by the OS initiative—both directly (e.g., researchers, institutions, policymakers) and indirectly (e.g., those who benefit from shared data access or downstream applications).

4. Identify and quantify costs and benefits for each stakeholder group

Building on the stakeholder mapping, the next step is to assess the specific costs and benefits associated with each group. This includes understanding their roles within the initiative and evaluating whether they are likely to gain advantages—such as improved efficiency, time savings, or enhanced collaboration—or face burdens, e.g. funding, contributing to resource updates, or efforts to maintain the initiative.

5. Set an appropriate time horizon

The fifth step involves setting a relevant time horizon over which costs and benefits will be assessed. This horizon should reflect the lifecycle of the OS initiative and its expected impacts. Where applicable, reference to the time horizon suggested by national and/or European guidelines for projects with similar features (e.g. research project, ICT projects) may provide valuable guidance in determining a suitable timeframe.

6. Collect data and synthesise results

With the framework established, the next phase is to collect data necessary to quantify the identified costs and benefits. This involves integrating diverse data sources, including platform usage statistics, financial records, user feedback, and expert judgment. Once data is collected, the results are synthesised to calculate total costs and benefits, enabling a comparison to assess the net value generated by the OS initiative. Where applicable, conduct sensitivity analyses to test the robustness of conclusions against key assumptions and uncertainties.

5.2. Future avenues

To maximise the effectiveness of the OS CBA framework in evaluating OS investments, the following actions are recommended:

- **Promote systematic data collection.** To support effective use of the OS CBA framework, a key priority is the routine collection of structured data—including usage patterns, user profiles, operational costs, and observed impacts. Case studies such as UniProt and RCAAP demonstrate that Open Science impacts can be assessed using a CBA approach; however, they also highlight current limitations in data availability—particularly for in-kind contributions, early-stage investments, and user time allocation. Developing and adopting standardised protocols for data collection—such as through

user surveys or systematic tracking of setup and operational costs—would enhance the applicability of the CBA framework and strengthen the robustness of its results. Importantly, even in the absence of in-house capacity to perform a full CBA, collecting relevant data lays the groundwork for future analysis and enables informed decision-making by external experts or institutional partners.

- **Strengthen institutional capacity for CBA.** Invest in training and tools to enable institutions to conduct or commission CBAs effectively. This entails building interdisciplinary expertise that combines economic evaluation with domain-specific knowledge, and equipping resource managers with practical tools to implement the CBA framework in routine assessments. Efforts in this direction would also benefit from the development of simplified, user-friendly templates tailored to different types of OS resources (e.g. repositories, platforms, software).
- **Embed CBA in funding and evaluation processes.** Incorporating CBA elements into project evaluation, selection, and impact reporting can enhance transparency and accountability in decision-making. Funding agencies and public institutions could require applicants to include basic CBA indicators or data collection plans within grant proposals. Likewise, ex-post assessments can leverage CBA metrics to evaluate programme outcomes and guide future resource allocation more effectively.

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Annexes

A. Glossary

CBA VOCABULARY	DEFINITION
B/C ratio	<p>It expresses the ratio between the present value of benefits and the present value of costs:</p> $B/C = \frac{\sum_{t=0}^T \frac{B_t}{(1+r)^t}}{\sum_{t=0}^T \frac{C_t}{(1+r)^t}}$ <p>A B/C ratio greater than 1 suggests that the initiative is socially beneficial, whereas a ratio below 1 implies that the costs outweigh the benefits. While the NPV remains the primary criterion, the B/C ratio can be particularly useful when comparing interventions of different scales.</p>
Counterfactual scenario	<p>The scenario that would have occurred in the absence of the project or policy. It serves as the benchmark against which the impacts of an intervention are measured. In cost-benefit analysis, the counterfactual is often referred to as the “without-project” scenario, and it can take various forms.</p>
Economic analysis	<p>A broader assessment that evaluates a project’s overall value to society, regardless of who bears the costs or receives the benefits. It includes externalities, public goods, and non-market effects, and uses shadow prices to reflect the true social value of resources. In the context of Open Science, economic analysis captures long-term benefits such as knowledge diffusion, innovation, and global accessibility.</p>
ENPV	<p>It is defined as the algebraic difference between the present value of benefits and the present value of costs over a specified time horizon. A positive ENPV indicates that the OS initiative is expected to generate a net gain in social welfare, while a negative ENPV signals that the resources employed could yield higher returns if allocated elsewhere. Formally, ENPV is computed as follows:</p> $ENPV = \sum_{t=0}^T \frac{B_t - C_t}{(1+r)^t}$
ERR	<p>it is the rate that produces a zero value for the ENPV; it satisfies the equation:</p> $0 = \sum_{t=0}^T \frac{B_t - C_t}{(1+r)^t}$
Externality	<p>A cost or benefit from an activity that affects others who are not directly involved. Open Science often generates positive externalities by enhancing knowledge spillovers.</p>
Financial analysis	<p>An assessment of a project’s monetary flows from the point of view of the implementing organisation or project owner. It considers actual revenues, expenditures, and cash flows. It answers the question: Is the project financially viable or sustainable for the organisation? In the case of Open Science, this might involve costs for setting up and maintaining a data repository, without accounting for wider societal benefits.</p>

Indirect and broader effects	Positive or negative consequences of a project that occur beyond its immediate objectives or target population. These effects may emerge over time or in other sectors, and are often not captured by direct financial flows. In the context of Open Science, indirect and broader effects may include enhanced international collaboration, improved public trust in science, spillovers to education and innovation ecosystems, or the strengthening of scientific capacities in low-resource settings. Recognising and, where possible, quantifying such effects is essential for a complete economic evaluation.
Marginal cost/benefit	The additional cost or benefit of producing or consuming one more unit of a good or service. Used to determine optimal investment levels.
Market failure	A situation where the market does not allocate resources efficiently on its own, justifying public intervention. Open Science aims to address some market failures in knowledge access.
Market value (price)	The price at which a good or service can be bought or sold in a competitive market. It reflects the amount that buyers are willing to pay and sellers are willing to accept, based on supply and demand. In cost-benefit analysis, market values are used to quantify costs and benefits when markets function well. However, many important effects of Open Science — such as increased access to knowledge or long-term societal benefits — do not have a market value, and require alternative methods like shadow pricing.
Opportunity cost	The value of the best alternative foregone when a resource is used for a particular purpose. It reflects the true economic cost of using that resource.
Present Value	The value today of a future cost or benefit, discounted using a chosen rate.
Public good	A good that is non-rival (one person's use does not reduce availability to others) and non-excludable (no one can be prevented from using it). Scientific knowledge is a typical example.
Shadow price	An estimated price used to value goods or services not traded in markets, such as time savings, clean air, or open data. Shadow prices are commonly used to reflect the true social opportunity cost of a resource or activity. They can be estimated through various empirical approaches, as extensively reviewed by Boardman et al. (2006), Brent (2006), De Rus (2010), Florio (2014), Potts (2002), Potts (2012a), and Boadway, (2006).
Shadow profit	An estimate of the economic profit generated by a project or activity, adjusted to reflect the true social value of inputs and outputs. Unlike accounting profit, shadow profit incorporates shadow prices, which correct for market distortions (e.g. taxes, subsidies, or monopolies), and reflects the opportunity cost of resources. It is used in CBA to assess the net contribution of a project to overall social welfare.
Shadow wage	An estimate of the true economic value of labour, reflecting its opportunity cost to society rather than its market wage. The shadow wage adjusts for distortions such as taxes, subsidies, unemployment, or informal employment and is used in CBA to more accurately value time and labour inputs. It often differs from observed wages and is particularly relevant in public sector or non-market evaluations.

Social Discount Rate	It is a key parameter used in the economic analysis of investment projects to discount future economic costs and benefits and to express them in terms of present values. It reflects the social view of how future benefits and costs are to be valued against present ones. In other words, it reflects the opportunity cost of capital for the whole society
Social welfare	The overall economic and non-economic well-being of society.
Sunk Cost	A cost that has already been incurred and cannot be recovered, regardless of future actions or decisions. In CBA, sunk costs are excluded from the appraisal of new investments because they do not represent an opportunity cost and should not influence the economic evaluation of future choices.
Utility	A measure of the satisfaction, benefit, or well-being that an individual derives from the consumption of goods and services or from engaging in certain activities. In economics and cost-benefit analysis, utility is a central concept used to represent individual preferences, although it is not directly observable and is typically inferred from choices, behaviours, or stated preferences.
Willingness to accept	The minimum compensation required for an individual to give up a good or accept a cost.
Willingness to pay	The maximum amount an individual is willing to pay for a good or service, often used to estimate the value of non-market benefits.

B. Approaches to Benefits and Costs estimation

This annex presents a reference of the well-established methodological approaches used to estimate the economic costs and benefits associated with OS project.

LONG-RUN MARGINAL SOCIAL COST³⁹

The long-run marginal social cost (LRMSC) of a good refers to the increase in the total cost to society—encompassing both private and external costs—required to expand the production of that good by one additional unit, while keeping the production levels of all other goods constant. In the context of OS, the LRMSC is particularly relevant for assessing the economic value of non-tradable inputs that must be scaled up in response to increased demand for open-access resources. To apply this method, the first step is to identify the specific good or service whose expansion is being analysed—for instance, the increase in data storage capacity within an OS data repository. The subsequent step involves estimating all additional costs associated with providing this expanded capacity. These may include the acquisition of new physical servers or cloud-based storage solutions, increased energy consumption for power and cooling, additional maintenance requirements, and the cost of technical staff responsible for managing the infrastructure. Where relevant, external costs—such as the environmental impact linked to higher electricity usage—should also be incorporated. Once all relevant costs are identified, they are divided by the number of additional storage units provided (e.g. cost per additional terabyte). For example, if expanding capacity by 100 terabytes entails a total incremental cost of €50,000, the resulting LRMSC would be €500 per terabyte. This value provides an estimate of the true societal cost of enhancing data availability and accessibility in OS settings, particularly where market prices are absent, or users access the service at no charge.

WILLINGNESS-TO-PAY AND WILLINGNESS-TO-ACCEPT⁴⁰

The (marginal) Willingness-to-Pay (WTP) represents the maximum amount of money that a consumer is willing to pay for an additional unit of a good or service, reflecting the perceived benefit derived from its consumption. In the context of this methodological note, WTP serves as an instrument for empirically estimating the direct benefits associated with OS resources, particularly given the non-market nature of many OS outputs. For example, WTP can be used to quantify the value that private firms, public sector organisations, or individual researchers place on access to a high-quality open database, or to a collaborative computing platform that expedites research and development activities. In such cases, where market prices are absent or unreliable, WTP provides an important proxy for capturing the user-

³⁹ Authors based on Florio (2014).

⁴⁰ Authors based on Jonsthon (2017); Carson (2011; 2012); Carson et al. (2005).

perceived benefit of OS services. WTP can also reflect the opportunity cost of key project inputs. For instance, the time investment required for researchers to become proficient in utilising a new OS resource represents a real cost in terms of foregone research, teaching, or administrative activities. The WTP to avoid or minimise this learning curve provides an implicit valuation of time savings, which constitutes an additional benefit attributable to OS interventions.

WTP can be estimated using both revealed and stated preference methods. Revealed preference approaches, such as the avoided cost method, infer WTP based on observed behaviours, for example by measuring the costs users avoid by accessing open resources instead of proprietary alternatives. Stated preference techniques, such as Contingent Valuation (CV) and Discrete Choice Modelling (DCM), elicit WTP directly from users by presenting hypothetical but policy-relevant scenarios. These methods are particularly important for OS initiatives, where direct market analogues may not exist and benefits are often diffuse and public in nature.

Nevertheless, particular attention must be given to the definition of the relevant population of beneficiaries and to potential sources of bias in WTP estimation, especially given the non-excludable and non-rival characteristics of many OS resources. Careful survey design, stakeholder consultation, and sensitivity analysis are therefore essential to ensure robust and policy relevant WTP estimates.

Under similar assumptions, **Willingness-to-Accept (WTA)** can be employed to assess the minimum compensation users would require to give up access to an OS resource, capturing the perceived loss associated with its unavailability. WTA is particularly relevant for valuing non-substitutable or highly integrated OS services, where withdrawal would disrupt ongoing activities. The key difference between WTP and WTA lies in the reference point: **WTP measures the value of gaining access, while WTA measures the value of foregoing it.** Empirical evidence consistently shows that WTA estimates tend to be higher than WTP for the same good, particularly when substitutes are limited or when individuals perceive strong entitlement to the resource. This disparity may reflect loss aversion and strategic bias. Considering the well-established difficulties associated with WTA, most empirical exercises opt for WTP. For these reasons, in what follows, the reference welfare measure is always WTP.⁴¹

AVOIDED COST METHOD⁴²

The avoided cost method estimates the economic value of a good or service by quantifying the costs that would have been incurred in the absence of the project or intervention. In the context of OS resource assessments, this method is particularly relevant for capturing indirect benefits and efficiency gains derived from freely accessible scientific outputs, infrastructures, or services. For example, if an open-access data repository enables researchers to reuse existing

⁴¹ For a detailed review of the differences between WTP and WTA see Kim, Kling, and Zhao (2015).

⁴² Florio (2014) for further details.

datasets rather than collect new data, the avoided costs of data collection activities—such as fieldwork, laboratory analysis, or licensing fees—can be considered a benefit attributable to the OS initiative. Similarly, OS tools that accelerate research processes may lead to reduced time-to-publication and lower duplication of effort, thereby avoiding personnel or overhead costs.

The method requires three main steps: (i) identifying a credible counterfactual scenario; (ii) estimating the costs that would have been incurred under that scenario; and (iii) attributing the difference to the OS intervention. Although conceptually straightforward, the method's practical application depends heavily on the availability of detailed cost data and the specification of a robust counterfactual.

A simplified operational approach to convert market prices into shadow prices involves **applying suitable conversion factors** to the main cost components considered in the financial analysis. These conversion factors can be derived from existing benchmarks established by national public authorities for CBA in other relevant fields. A conversion factor is defined as the ratio between shadow prices and market prices, serving as the multiplier by which market prices must be adjusted to obtain the corresponding shadow price.⁴³

Notably, particular emphasis should be placed on the **opportunity cost of labour**, which is assessed using the concept of the shadow wage. The shadow wage rate signifies the social opportunity cost of labour and may diverge from the observed wage due to labour-related distortions, such as unemployment, migration, taxes, and minimum wages, as well as factors present in the product markets. In accordance with the opportunity cost concept, the shadow wage should accurately reflect the social benefit of employing an individual in a specific region, country, and sector characterised by distinct labour market conditions, as opposed to other alternatives. By carefully considering the shadow wage and employing conversion factors, the simplified operational approach enables the estimation of OS costs in shadow prices, facilitating a more comprehensive and accurate economic evaluation.⁴⁴

A primary operational approach is **market substitution**, whereby avoided costs are approximated by identifying the price of a comparable closed or proprietary service. This includes, for instance, subscription fees for scientific journals, paywalled databases, proprietary analytical software, or other research tools that fulfil a similar function. Given the variability in the nature of OS resources and the diversity of user needs, no universal data source exists from which to derive cost savings. Analysts must therefore conduct targeted market research to identify the most appropriate commercial equivalents for the OS service under evaluation. For example, when assessing the value of open-source software, a functionally equivalent proprietary package available on the market can serve as the benchmark.

⁴³ See Florio et al. 2016 for further details on the application of RDI projects and additional literature.

⁴⁴ The CBA literature offers different shadow wage formulas on the basis of the different hypothesis on labour and product market conditions. Recent theoretical contributions include Potts (2002); Londero (2003); de Rus (2010); and Potts (2012b). Recent empirical contributions include Honohan (1998); Saleh (2004); Picazo-Tadeo and Reig-Martinez (2005); and Del Bo et al. (2011). The latter presents a new, simple framework for the empirical computation of shadow wages at the regional level and empirical estimations for EU regions.

While the exact structure of avoided cost estimation may vary depending on the type of OS input under consideration, a general formula can be summarised as follows:

$$\text{Access Cost Savings} = \sum_{t=0}^T \sum_{i=1}^N p(q, t, N) * q_t$$

Where:

q_t might be the number of research outputs (journals, data, methods, tools) that might vary over time and might be counted depending on the type of the OS (e.g., a single article, an annual access, etc.);

$p(q, t, N)$ is the market price that can vary depending on the type of OS and over time. For instance, an enterprise might opt for paying the price of single articles having an annual budget instead of illimited access, which is usually chosen by research institutions. The same applies to data access, which prices might change depending on the type of data, the frequency, etc.;

$t=0, \dots, T$ is the period over which the benefit should be computed;

$i=1, \dots, N$ is the number of users involved that might vary over time and can affect the price, e.g., the access to software might depend on the number of users.

In addition to market-based valuation, the **opportunity cost of time savings** provides an important and complementary dimension for quantifying avoided costs. Time savings represent a significant benefit, particularly in professional and research contexts where time is a critical production input. Such savings may result from faster access to structured datasets, reduced duplication of research efforts, or streamlined integration of information into research workflows.

The monetisation of time savings is typically achieved by applying a value to users' time, based either on their individual wage rates or on average sector-specific labour costs. Beneficiaries should ideally provide salary data for each employee category involved, along with estimates of the number of hours saved. If individual wage data are unavailable, salary benchmarks from private-sector human resource databases can be used. In cases where such benchmarks are also unavailable, national statistical institutes generally provide average labour cost data per hour, commonly used for productivity analyses. Where necessary, sectoral wage differentials can be applied to refine estimates. For cross-country comparisons, harmonised labour cost data can be retrieved from sources such as the OECD productivity indicators.

The benefit derived from time savings can be expressed as:

$$\text{Labour Cost Savings} = \sum_{t=0}^T \sum_{i=1}^N h_{it} * w_{it}$$

Where:

h_{it} is the individual time saved;

w_{it} is the individual hourly cost of labour;

$t = 0, \dots, T$ is the span of time over which the benefit should be computed;

$i = 1, \dots, N$ is the number of professionals involved in the time saving.

CONTINGENT VALUATION OR DISCRETE CHOICE MODELLING TO ESTIMATE WILLINGNESS TO PAY⁴⁵

Demand-side valuation methods can provide complementary insights on methods like LRMSC by estimating how much individuals or organisations are willing to pay for access to such services. In this regard, Contingent Valuation and Discrete Choice Modelling are two widely used stated preference techniques for eliciting WTP (or WTA) in the absence of observable market transactions.

CV is a stated preference method used to estimate individuals' WTP for non-market goods and services by presenting them with a hypothetical but policy-relevant scenario (in the context of OS see the applications of Beagrie and Houton 2021 and 2016 on the evaluation of EMBL-EBI data resources). CV surveys typically ask respondents whether they would be willing to pay a specified amount for a proposed improvement (e.g. improved access to an Open Data repository) or to avoid a loss (e.g. discontinuation of a collaborative OS service). Key components of a well-designed CV application include:

- A clear and neutral description of the good or service being valued;
- A realistic payment vehicle, such as a user fee, donation, or public fund contribution;
- A plausible and policy-relevant valuation scenario;
- A question format (e.g. dichotomous choice or payment card) that minimises cognitive burden and strategic responses.

Following best practice guidelines—such as those established by Johnston et al. (2017)—is essential to ensure the validity and reliability of CV results. These include careful pre-testing, bias mitigation (e.g. hypothetical and embedding effects), and ensuring that the survey instrument communicates all relevant information in a clear and accessible manner.

DCM is an alternative stated preference method that estimates WTP by observing respondents' choices among hypothetical alternatives, each described by a combination of attributes and associated costs. DCM is useful for evaluating multi-attribute services (see for instance the application by Koudouri et al. (2021) in evaluating the benefit of the OpenAIRE project). Instead of asking for a direct monetary valuation, DCM presents respondents with a series of choice sets, each consisting of two or more alternatives, and asks them to select their preferred option. The design allows for the estimation of marginal WTP for specific attributes by analysing the trade-offs respondents are willing to make between different features and associated costs. Application steps include:

- Identifying relevant attributes and levels through stakeholder consultation and pilot testing;
- Developing an experimental design that systematically varies attribute combinations across choice sets;

⁴⁵ Authors based on Jonsthor (2017); Carson (2011; 2012); Carson et al. (2005).

- Collecting data via a structured survey;
- Estimating choice models (e.g. multinomial or mixed logit) to derive WTP for each attribute.

A critical challenge in applying stated preference techniques in the context of Open Science arises when the user population is unknown or only partially defined. Unlike traditional infrastructure or services with clearly identifiable beneficiaries (e.g. transport users or utility customers), OS initiatives often produce non-excludable and non-rival public goods—such as open-access data or freely available tools—whose benefits may extend to a broad and heterogeneous group of users, including future or indirect beneficiaries. This lack of a well-defined target population poses methodological difficulties in designing representative surveys and aggregating individual WTP responses to obtain a total economic value. It also raises questions about whose preferences should be elicited—only current users, the general public, or specific stakeholder groups (e.g. researchers, educators, industry)? If the sample is not representative of the relevant beneficiary base, WTP estimates may either understate or overstate societal value. Moreover, in the absence of a known user base, selecting an appropriate payment vehicle (e.g. voluntary donation vs. public funding) becomes more complex, potentially affecting the realism and credibility of the valuation scenario. As recommended by Johnston et al. (2017), in such cases, special attention should be paid to sampling strategies, the scope and framing of the survey, and the use of sensitivity analysis to explore how results may vary under different assumptions about the beneficiary population.

Once obtained the willingness-to-pay for a unit of time (e.g., yearly) across the survey respondents, the value of the access cost savings equals:

$$\text{Access Cost Savings: } \overline{WTP} * N * T$$

Where:

\overline{WTP} is the average willingness to pay;

N is the estimated number of users;

T is the span of time chosen for the evaluation of the benefit.

INCREMENTAL SHADOW PROFITS⁴⁶

The incremental shadow profits method estimates the economic value of a project by quantifying the additional profits generated as a result of its implementation, adjusted using shadow prices—that is, prices corrected for market distortions such as taxes, subsidies, or unpriced externalities. This method is particularly relevant for assessing the benefits associated with innovations enabled by OS resources, as discussed in Section 4.2.1. It captures the increase in firms' or organisations' economic surplus that can be causally attributed to the availability of open-access scientific outputs, infrastructures, or services.

⁴⁶ See Florio et al. (2016) for further details.

The method involves comparing projected profits under two scenarios: with and without the OS intervention. Input and output values are adjusted using appropriate shadow prices to reflect their true social opportunity cost, ensuring that the resulting estimates of economic surplus are consistent with broader welfare impacts rather than purely financial gains. For example, if access to data shared through an OS platform enables a firm to develop a new product or to enhance an existing technology, the resulting increase in profits—once corrected for market distortions—can be considered a proxy for the project's broader economic contribution.

The assessment of this benefit firstly requires the quantification of the demand for each innovation over the evaluation period. In the case of the creation of start-ups, it involves identifying the newly established companies enabled by OS resources. Subsequently, the estimation of expected profits associated with each innovation or start-up can be carried out.

Once estimated the expected profits associated with each enablement, the social value $E(Z)$ is equal to:

$$E(Z) = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{t=0}^T \{E(\Pi)_{it}\}$$

Where:

$i=1, \dots, N$ is the number of the enablements (products, services, technologies, and start-ups)

$t=0, \dots, T$ is the span of time over which the benefit should be computed and can be expressed in any unit of time.

$E(\Pi)_{it}$ is the expected shadow profit associated with any enablement

ESTIMATING THE MARGINAL SOCIAL VALUE OF PATENTS AND LICENCES⁴⁷

The marginal social value (MSV) of patents and licences method estimates the economic benefit generated through intellectual property outputs entirely associated with an OS project. Specifically, it captures both the private returns to innovators (e.g., firms or researchers) and the positive externalities that patents and licences generate for the broader scientific and technological community. This method recognises that while the private value of a patent reflects the increased profits accruing to its holder, a significant portion of the social value stems from knowledge spillovers that enhance productivity and innovation elsewhere in the economy.

The estimation process involves several steps. First, the incremental number of patents expected to result from OS practices must be forecasted. This is typically based on historical performance, promoter-specific data, or benchmarks from similar infrastructures. Second, the average usage rate of patents is projected, often using data on patent citations as a proxy for technological influence.⁴⁸ Third, the marginal private value of each patent is estimated, while

⁴⁷ See Florio et al. (2016) for further details.

⁴⁸ In Bryan and Ozcan (2021) it has been shown that in-text patent citations might be a more accurate way of counting the number of references compared to front page citation.

ensuring that any overlap with incremental shadow profits is properly addressed to avoid double counting. Finally, the externality component—representing the broader knowledge diffusion impact—is quantified, for example, by assigning a monetary value to forward citations or broader innovation benefits.

Formally, the social value $E(P)$ is calculated as:

$$E(P) = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{t=0}^T \{E(MSV)\}_{(pv_{it}, ex_{it})}$$

where:

$i=1, \dots, N$ is the number of the patents

$t=0, \dots, T$ is the span of time over which the benefit should be computed and can be expressed in any unit of time

$E(MSV)\}_{(pv_{it}, ex_{it})}$ is the marginal social value (MSV) that includes both the private value (pv_{it}) and the externality (ex_{it})

BENEFIT TRANSFER

Benefit transfer is a valuation technique widely applied in cost-benefit analysis when conducting primary data collection is not possible or would be disproportionately costly. It involves using existing estimates of economic values, typically derived from studies conducted in one location or context (the study site), and applying them to a different location, population, or policy intervention (the policy site). The underlying rationale is that values for similar goods or services—such as time savings, environmental amenities, or knowledge spillovers—can be transferred across contexts, thereby reducing the need for new valuation exercises.

There are two main approaches: value transfer, which applies an average value or a unit value from previous studies, and function transfer, which adapts entire demand or benefit functions to the new context, sometimes adjusting for socio-economic or demographic differences. While benefit transfer is cost-effective and facilitates the inclusion of non-market impacts, its accuracy depends critically on the degree of similarity between study and policy sites, and on the quality of the original studies. Poorly matched or outdated transfers can lead to substantial errors in valuation.